

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 2: Evolutionary Computation module – part 1: Basics and single-objective optimization

Michał K. Tomczyk

Institute of Computing Science, Poznan University of Technology, Poznań, Poland

This document is part of a tutorial series on JECDM. URL: www.jecdm.cs.put.poznan.pl, email: jecdm@cs.put.poznan.pl.
The framework version used when preparing the document: 1.0 (initial release; Java v. 17.0; IntelliJ IDEA 2023.2).

Abstract

This tutorial discusses the Evolutionary Computation module. It showcases the module’s general capabilities and provides concrete examples of using it in practice.

Keywords: JECDM, evolutionary computation, evolutionary algorithm, optimization

Contents

1 Introduction	2		
2 Understanding fundamental concepts	2		
2.1 Three-level hierarchical structure	2	2.8.11 Merge (PHASE_MERGE)	16
2.2 A reference scheme of an evolutionary algorithm	2	2.8.12 Update objective space (PHASE_UPDATE_OBJECTIVE_SPACE)	16
2.3 Specimen	3	2.8.13 Remove (REMOVE_PHASE)	16
2.4 Specimen container	5	2.8.14 Finalize step	17
2.5 Objective space manager	6	2.9 Summary of default phases and imposed flow .	17
2.6 Phases (interface and the abstract class)	6	2.10 Bundle classes	17
2.7 Evolutionary algorithm	8	2.10.1 Phases bundle	17
2.8 Default implementations of phases	11	2.10.2 Abstract EA bundle	19
2.8.1 Initialization starts (PHASE_INIT_STARTS)	12	2.10.3 Problem bundle	21
2.8.2 Construct initial population (PHASE_CONSTRUCT_INITIAL_POPULATION)	12	2.11 Runner	22
2.8.3 Assign specimens IDs (PHASE_ASSIGN_SPECIMENS_IDS)	12	2.11.1 On the visualization mode	24
2.8.4 Evaluate (PHASE_EVALUATE)	13	3 Example implementation for solving a knapsack problem [T]	27
2.8.5 Sort (PHASE_SORT)	14	3.1 Problem definition	27
2.8.6 Initialization ends (PHASE_INIT_ENDS)	14	3.2 Solution approach	27
2.8.7 Prepare step (PREPARE_STEP)	14	3.3 Designed algorithm	28
2.8.8 Construct mating pool (PHASE_CONSTRUCT_MATING_POOL) 14		3.3.1 Data container	28
2.8.9 Select parents (PHASE_SELECT_PARENTS)	15	3.3.2 Constructor	29
2.8.10 Reproduce (PHASE_REPRODUCE)	15	3.3.3 Reproducer	30
		3.3.4 Evaluator	31
		3.3.5 Algorithm bundle	32
		3.3.6 Instantiating the evolutionary algorithm	33
		3.4 Example experiments	34
		3.4.1 Creating and running the algorithm	34
		3.4.2 Using the Runner object	35
		3.4.3 Reporting the performance using a scatter plot	35
		3.4.4 Combining results of different runs	37
		3.4.5 Reporting the performance using a con- vergence plot	37
		3.4.6 Reporting the performance using a multi-plot visualization window	38

Email address: michal.tomczyk@cs.put.poznan.pl (Michał K. Tomczyk)
URL: www.cs.put.poznan.pl/mtomczyk (Michał K. Tomczyk)

4	Example implementation for maximizing a continuous function of two variables [T]	39
4.1	Problem definition	39
4.2	Solution approach	39
4.3	Designed algorithm	39
4.3.1	Constructor	41
4.3.2	Reproducer	42
4.3.3	Evaluator	43
4.4	Example experiments	44
4.4.1	Creating and running the algorithm . .	44
4.4.2	Reporting the performance using a scatter plot (the last generation)	44
4.4.3	Reporting the performance using a scatter plot (all generations)	46
4.4.4	Reporting the performance using a multi-plot visualization window	47

1. Introduction

Important note

A major change in the hierarchy of the core *EA* class (discussed in this document) was done in v. 1.06.21.08.2025 of this framework. It is discussed in the “*Tutorial 13: Change in the hierarchy of the EA class*” tutorial document. In short, *EA* is not now the highest in the hierarchy. Instead, a dedicated interface *IEA* was derived, and *EA* implements it. This change intends to introduce greater generalization of the code. Now, the relevant processing relies on passing instances of *IEA*, not *EA* (which may raise some minor compatibility issues with the previous versions). Nonetheless, be aware that this document is not updated to meet this change, and still treats *EA* as the class highest in the hierarchy.

End of the note

This tutorial introduces a module dedicated to evolutionary computation, a powerful tool for solving optimization problems. The document is divided into two major parts. First, Section 2 delves into the fundamental concepts implemented in JECDM, such as specimen, objective space, mating pool, or top-level class hierarchy. The remaining sections will demonstrate how the module can be practically applied to solve selected optimization problems. It is important to note that this document primarily focuses on single-objective optimization, while the following tutorial focuses on the multi-objective case. It is assumed that you, the reader, already have a solid understanding of evolutionary computation. Consequently, the document will not cover theoretical fundamentals. Instead, it focuses on how experienced practitioners, such as teachers, researchers, or developers, can effectively use the module’s implementations in practice.

An evolutionary algorithm is a metaheuristic, meaning that it is a very general and problem-independent algorithmic concept. In some sense, it can be considered a set of guidelines for implementing one’s own optimizer inspired by natural processes.

The primary goal when developing this framework was to treat evolutionary computation precisely this way instead of being unquestioningly focused on providing hard-coded and concrete implementations. To achieve such implementation elasticity, the module was established on the concept of phase. A large part of this document is devoted to this concept in later sections. As for now, a phase can be considered a small functional block dedicated to performing some operations (e.g., reproducing solutions), while the evolutionary process can be thought about as a process that emerges from suitably implementing and organized phases. Not only is excellent flexibility provided in this way, but using the functional blocks also allows for maximizing code reusability.

It is worth noting that despite their different hierarchical orders, the evolutionary computation module is discussed before the decision support one. The latter module is primarily considered a supplementary component to the evolutionary one in this framework. For instance, it is used to implement preference-driven evolutionary algorithms. Therefore, it makes more sense to introduce the evolutionary computation module first, as it forms the foundation for the decision support module.

2. Understanding fundamental concepts

This section introduces the most fundamental concepts implemented in this module. For convenience, localizations of relevant source code packages will accompany the following subsections.

2.1. Three-level hierarchical structure

Consider a spectrum starting with implementing the smallest functional blocks and ending with executing an evolutionary algorithm. Although many classes can typically be employed within such a scope, they can be generally divided into three fundamental layers in JECDM (see Figure 1).

First, the bottom-level classes are the already mentioned phases. It is worth considering implementing these lowest-level functionalities first when designing an evolutionary algorithm using JECDM. These blocks are supposed to realize some steps, but they should have no control over their execution. It is a prerogative of an evolutionary algorithm. This middle-level layer (class) is responsible for data handling and organizing how the phases are executed, ensuring that the emerged process behaves as intended to do so. Finally, the highest-level layer, a runner, is responsible for correctly running the evolutionary process. It also can be considered the highest-level controller coupled with other frameworks’ functionalities (e.g., visualization or experimentation module).

2.2. A reference scheme of an evolutionary algorithm

This section aims to deliver and briefly discuss probably the most standard and widely used scheme of an evolutionary algorithm (pseudocode). It will serve as a reference point when delving more deeply into various components implemented within this framework.

Figure 1: The three-level structure

First, an evolutionary algorithm is a nature-inspired metaheuristic that optimizes a set of solutions \mathbf{P} called a population. The algorithm iteratively improves the members in \mathbf{P} by recombining them, constructing new (offspring) solutions, and applying the so-called survival-of-the-fittest rule for preserving only the best solutions according to the optimized function.

Consider now the pseudo delineated in Algorithm 1. The algorithm starts with constructing an initial population of solutions \mathbf{P}^0 of size N (line 1). A dedicated procedure can be used for this purpose (e.g., a local-search-based one), but it is often assumed that these solutions are generated randomly. Then, they are assigned their fitness scores, i.e., evaluated by the assumed objective function f (line 2). Overall, lines 1-2 can be considered an initialization step.

Algorithm 1 A general scheme of an evolutionary algorithm.

- Input:** N – a size of the population; G – the number of generations; method-specific operators, objective function f ;
Output: \mathbf{P} – the final population
- 1: $\mathbf{P}^0 \leftarrow$ create an initial population of size N
 - 2: Evaluate solutions in \mathbf{P}^0 as imposed by f
 - 3: **for** $g = 0, \dots, G - 1$ **do**
 - 4: $\mathbf{P}^p \leftarrow$ select parent solutions for reproduction from \mathbf{P}^g
 - 5: $\mathbf{P}^o \leftarrow$ generate offspring solutions by applying reproduction operators on solutions in \mathbf{P}^p
 - 6: Evaluate solutions in \mathbf{P}^o as imposed by f
 - 7: $\mathbf{P}^{g+1} \leftarrow \mathbf{P}^g \cup \mathbf{P}^o$
 - 8: Apply the survival-of-the-fittest rule on \mathbf{P}^{g+1}
 - 9: **return** \mathbf{P}^G

Lines 3-8 represent the main loop linked to the evolutionary process. Every iteration represents a single so-called generation. The total number of such epochs reached, denoted by G , is often assumed to be the stopping criterion (line 3). Commonly, each generation starts with identifying parent solutions \mathbf{P}^p for reproduction in the current population \mathbf{P}^g (line 4). This process is called selection. Although fundamentally randomized, the selection favors solutions in \mathbf{P}^g that are of good quality, increasing chances for generating better offspring.

The reproduction step takes solutions in \mathbf{P}^p as the input. It applies reproduction operators to the parent solutions to generate the offspring population \mathbf{P}^o of a desired size (typically N , line 5). This step can be implemented in various ways, follow-

ing different reproduction patterns. However, most commonly, it is assumed that one offspring solution is generated from a pair of selected parents by applying the crossover operator followed by the mutation one. Consequently, \mathbf{P}^p can take the form of an N -element list of pairs, where each pair is used to construct a different offspring.

A well-designed crossover operator intends to ensure that the offspring inherit some favorable properties from its parents. Such an implemented operator ensures an efficient exploitation of the promising region in the solution space during optimization. Note that a highly randomized crossover that produces offspring unlike its parents will tend to hinder evolution. Implementing such an operator is a common mistake made by less-experienced developers. However, slight – but controlled – perturbations in search are desired as they may help escape local optima, permitting thus exploration. The mutation operator can be applied to introduce such a controlled randomization.

After constructing \mathbf{P}^o , its solutions are evaluated using the assumed objective function f (line 6). In line 7, \mathbf{P}^o is combined with the current population \mathbf{P}^g , forming the candidates \mathbf{P}^{g+1} to be passed to the next generation. The generation often ends with removing from \mathbf{P}^{g+1} N solutions that attain the worst f -values (although they also may be put into an external archive). This step is referred to as survival-of-the-fittest (line 8). If the limit for the number of generations is reached, the loop is terminated, and the algorithm returns the final population \mathbf{P}^G .

2.3. Specimen

Acquainting yourself with this module should start with the *Specimen* class (*population* package). This class represents a solution (specimen is a biological term). Consider its selected code snippets in Listing 1. Noticeably, the specimen class implements the *IAlternativeWrapper* that is introduced to help treat a collection of specimens as a collection of alternatives, e.g., for iterating (see *alternatives.IAlternativeWrapper* in the *DecisionSupport* module).

Listing 1: Specimen class

```

/**
 * Class representing a specimen.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class Specimen implements
    IAlternativeWrapper
{
    /**
     * Chromosome object used to represent a
     * solution in the genetic/decision/
     * phenotypic/problem-specific space.
     */
    protected Chromosome _chromosome;

    /**
     * ({@link alternative.Alternative})
     * object is primarily used to represent
     * a solution in the objective space,
     * but

```

```

    * also it provides a bridge between the
      DecisionSupport module and the
      EvolutionaryComputation module.
    */
protected Alternative _alternative;

/**
 * Unique ID assigned to a specimen.
 */
protected SpecimenID _id;

[...]

/**
 * Setter for the evaluation vector (
   objective space). The method
   terminates if the alternative object
   is not instantiated.
 *
 * @param evaluations evaluation vector
 */
public void setEvaluations(double[]
    evaluations)
{
    if (_alternative == null) return;
    _alternative.setPerformance(evaluations
        );
}

/**
 * Getter for the evaluation vector (
   objective space). The method returns
   null if the alternative object is not
   instantiated.
 *
 * @return evaluation vector
 */
public double[] getEvaluations()
{
    if (_alternative == null) return null;
    return _alternative.getPerformance();
}
}

```

The *Specimen* class contains three fundamental fields: chromosome, alternative, and id. The chromosome field (*Chromosome* class in the *population* package) is supposed to store the fundamental data on the particular solution instance. It is highly implementation-dependent, but generally, one can consider it a solution representation in a selected space, e.g., genetic, decision, or phenotypic. For instance, a chromosome may be defined as a simple decision vector. However, the *Chromosome* class allows setting more complex implementations. Consider the Listing 2 that showcases the *Chromosome* and *Gene* classes. As can be observed, the *Chromosome* is a simple wrapper for the *Gene* array (various auxiliary setters and getters are provided in the *Chromosome* class to facilitate data storing and retrieving). In turn, the *Gene* class allows setting an integer, double, and boolean vector, providing great flexibility in solu-

tion modeling. Moreover, establishing a graph-like (e.g., tree-like structure) gene structure is also supported because a gene object can store references to other genes. In summary, remembering the following class hierarchy when modeling a solution: *Specimen* → *Chromosome* → *Genes* is worth memorizing.

Listing 2: Chromosome and Gene classes

```

public class Chromosome
{
    /**
     * Vector of genes ({@link population.
       Gene}).
     */
    public Gene[] _genes;

    [...]
}

public class Gene
{
    /**
     * Vector of doubles.
     */
    public double[] _dv;

    /**
     * Vector of integers.
     */
    public int[] _iv;

    /**
     * Vector of booleans.
     */
    public boolean[] _bv;

    /**
     * References to other genes (e.g., tree-
       like dependencies can be defined).
       Cyclic references should be avoided.
     */
    public Gene[] _gene;

    /**
     * Auxiliary variable that can be used
       when defining more complex
       dependencies ( = 0 by default).
     */
    public int _level;

    [...]
}

```

The following fundamental field in the *Specimen* class is the “*_alternative*”. Note that the *Alternative* class belongs to the *DecisionSupport* module (*alternative* package). This object is intended to store the data on the solution performance (e.g., according to the employed objective function). See the code Listing 3 that showcases the *Alternative* class. Its two fields, *_name* and *_performance*, are self-explanatory. When it comes to the “*_auxScores*” field, it was introduced to allow associat-

ing some meta-information (scores) with an alternative. Such an auxiliary score may be used, e.g., to store the overall (final fitness score) attained by the specimen used in a dedicated sorting procedure to determine which solutions should be passed to the next generation and which should be rejected (e.g., non-dominated sorting in NSGA-II [3]).

Listing 3: Alternative class

```

public class Alternative implements
    IAlternativeWrapper
{
    /**
     * Name of the alternative.
     */
    private String _name;

    /**
     * Performance vector.
     */
    private double[] _performance;

    /**
     * Vector of auxiliary scores attained by
     * the alternative.
     */
    private double[] _auxScores;

    [...]
}

```

Lastly, the “*id*” field stores unique identification data. The *SpecimenID* class (*population* package) is a simple implementation of a 4-element integer tuple: (ID of a genetic algorithm, generation number when constructed, steady-state number when constructed, unique in-population number). Important note: The ID is assigned automatically by the algorithm in default implementations (a dedicated phase implements this functionality; this will be discussed in later parts of this document). Generally, it is recommended not to modify the ID once assigned or change it manually (though the *SpecimenID* is an immutable class). Also, the “steady-state number” may require additional elaboration. When an evolutionary method generates just one solution in a single iteration, it is often called a steady-state algorithm. This framework supports not only running in a standard steady-state mode but also mixing the generational and steady-state one. When it comes to the latter, it is assumed that a single iteration number is defined as a two-element tuple: (generation number; steady-state repeat number). The runner mentioned in Section 2.1 steers the evolutionary process by processing two nested loops, where the external one is responsible for controlling the current generation while the internal controls the current steady-state repeat number. A single iteration of the algorithm is thus provided, as an input, the timestamp, which is the tuple mentioned above. The information on the current generation and steady-state repeat numbers is stored when assigning a unique ID to the specimen. Nonetheless, these aspects will be discussed more extensively later in this document.

Note that this section intentionally omits setter- and getter-

like methods in the code listings, as their purpose is often self-explanatory. A brief code inspection is all the programmer needs to understand how they work. It is thus up to the user to become acquainted themselves with them.

2.4. Specimen container

The next class worth focusing on is *population.SpecimenContainer*. This class plays the role of a top-level container for solutions generated throughout the evolutionary process. Its initial implementation allows for setting solution arrays that reflect the current population, mating pool (solutions permitted to be picked as parent solutions, usually a subset of the current population), parent solutions designated for reproduction (see the *population.Parents* class), and offspring (see the relevant code snippet of the *SpecimenContainer* class brought in Listing 4). Note that this framework has not yet explicitly implemented the archive functionality. However, it is in plans for future developments, and it is assumed that the archive will be a member of the specimen container.

The class also contains four auxiliary fields. The “_populationRequiresEvaluation” and “_offspringRequiresEvaluation” fields can be suitably set to indicate whether the newly set solutions have (or have not) been evaluated. Similarly, “_populationRequiresIDAssignment” and “_offspringRequiresIDAssignment” flags determine whether the specimens stored in the population of offspring array require ID assignment.

Listing 4: SpecimenContainer class

```

public class SpecimensContainer
{
    /**
     * The population = array of specimens.
     */
    private ArrayList<Specimen> _population;

    /**
     * Array of parents selected for mating.
     */
    private ArrayList<Parents> _parents;

    /**
     * The generated offspring.
     */
    private ArrayList<Specimen> _offspring;

    /**
     * A field representing a mating pool.
     * Can be used if needed. It can be, e.g
     * ., considered as a selected subset of
     * specimens from the current
     * population.
     */
    private ArrayList<Specimen> _matingPool;

    /**
     * Auxiliary flag indicating whether the
     * population requires evaluation.
     */
}

```

```

private boolean
    _populationRequiresEvaluation = false;

/**
 * Auxiliary flag indicating whether the
 * offspring requires evaluation.
 */
private boolean
    _offspringRequiresEvaluation = false;

/**
 * Auxiliary flag indicating whether the
 * population requires ID assignment.
 */
private boolean
    _populationRequiresIDAssignment =
        false;

/**
 * Auxiliary flag indicating whether the
 * offspring requires ID assignment.
 */
private boolean
    _offspringRequiresIDAssignment = false
;

[...]
}

```

2.5. Objective space manager

The *ObjectiveSpaceManager* class (*os* package) is brought here just for the sake of completeness, as it is more relevant to multi-objective optimization (this document concerns a single-objective optimization). In short, this class plays a similar role to the *DisplayRangesManager* in the *Visualization* module. It handles data associated with the min-max identified values for each objective (the knowledge of these ranges is essential in multi-objective optimization). It also introduces a simple notification mechanism to report linked listeners on changes in these bounds that occurred when, e.g., moving from one generation to the next. Overall, this class and its use will be discussed more extensively in the following document, i.e., “*Tutorial 3: Evolutionary Computation module – part 2: multi-objective optimization*”

2.6. Phases (interface and the abstract class)

As previously explained, phases are the functional blocks that make up an evolutionary algorithm. They offer a high degree of flexibility and can be adapted and utilized when creating a specific method implementation. By breaking down the overall evolutionary process into a series of such blocks, it becomes easier to develop new approaches, enhance code reusability, and implement reliable, error-safe procedures.

This framework has implemented many predefined phases that can be considered default. However, they will be introduced after the *ea.EvolutionaryAlgorithm* class to enhance the reading flow.

Consider Figure 2 that showcases the types hierarchy of phase-based sources. First, there is an interface *phase.IPhase* at the top. Its code is provided in Listing 5 for convenience. Noticeably, there is just one “core” method signature (+ return type): “*PhaseReport perform(EA ea) throws PhaseException*”. The implemented functional block is supposed to be executed via this method.

Figure 2: Phases – types hierarchy

Listing 5: IPhase interface

```

public interface IPhase
{
    /**
     * Executes the phase.
     *
     * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
     * @throws PhaseException the exception
     *         can be thrown and propagated higher
     */
    PhaseReport perform(EA ea) throws
        PhaseException;

    /**
     * Returns the phase name
     *
     * @return name
     */
    String getName();

    /**
     * Returns phase unique identifier (see {
     *     @link PhasesIDs}).
     *
     * @return ID
     */
    int getID();
}

```

Before proceeding, let’s briefly discuss the return, input, and throwable associated with the above method (signature + type). The method is expected to return a report on its performance (see *phase.PhaseReport* class). Currently, the *PhaseReport* class provides fields related to calculating the action execution time, but this may change in the future (extra fields can be added).

Regarding the input, the method is passed the reference to the evolutionary algorithm itself (*ea.EA*; this primary class will be discussed more extensively in Section 2.7). This class provides various getters that a phase is allowed to use during processing. Providing such an almost unrestricted access is typically considered a bad coding practice. However, a specific implemen-

tation of an evolutionary algorithm, is a product of algorithmic development and should be viewed as a closed/consolidated entity. Thus, it is up to the researcher/scientist/developer to ensure the algorithm's internal safety and correctness. In this view, providing more restricted access could hinder the development.

Finally, the method is allowed to throw *exception.PhaseException*. Note that, however, the exception system in this module is very primitive and limited and should not be overused (should be used only in very exceptional situations). The reason for not developing a more advanced exception system was the fact that the developed algorithms, as closed entities, should be error-safe from the beginning, which should have already been ensured during the development. An exception system is something that should be used when something genuinely unexpected can happen (e.g., reading data from an external drive that can be unplugged).

Consider now *phase.AbstractPhase* class that provides common fields and functionalities for all implemented predefined phases. Its most relevant code snippets are in Listing 6.

First, a phase should be supplied with a name and a unique ID (see *phase.PhasesIDs* class). The extending classes (the predefined ones) will automatically provide these parameters by calling super in their constructors (predefined names and IDs will be passed). The ID (integer) plays the role of an index used when accessing phases that are stored in an array in the evolutionary algorithm class.

Next, consider the core “perform” method (from the *IPhase* interface). It creates the phase report first, which will be filled during processing. Noticeably, the processing is split into three auxiliary methods: “preAction”, “action”, and “postAction” (similar splitting is often used in JECDM); each is supplied with a reference to the evolutionary algorithm and the report. Finally, the report is returned after the processing is done.

The “pre” and “post” actions are reserved for some system-related, technical implementations. In this initial release of JECDM, they are used to conditionally measure the execution time of the main action. Conversely, the “action” method is intended to be overwritten by extending classes (is initially empty). The supplied predefined phases typically extend only this method, minimizing thus code redundancy.

Listing 6: AbstractPhase class

```

public abstract class AbstractPhase
    implements IPhase
{
    /**
     * The name of the phase.
     */
    public final String _name;

    /**
     * Unique ID number.
     */
    protected final int _id;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     */
}

```

```

    * @param name name of the phase
    * @param id phase id
    */
public AbstractPhase(String name, int id)
{
    _name = name;
    _id = id;
}

/**
 * Executes the pre-action, main action,
 * and post action.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @return report on the executed action
 * @throws PhaseException the exception
 *         can be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public PhaseReport perform(EA ea) throws
    PhaseException
{
    PhaseReport report = new PhaseReport();
    preAction(ea, report);
    action(ea, report);
    postAction(ea, report);
    return report;
}

/**
 * Executes a step preceding the main
 * action.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 *         action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception
 *         can be thrown and propagated higher
 */
public void preAction(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
{
    if ((ea.getComputeExecutionTimes() ||
        ea.getComputePhasesExecutionTimes()
        )
        )
        report._startTime = System.nanoTime()
        ;
}

/**
 * Executes the main action of the phase
 * (to be overwritten).
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 *         action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception
 *         can be thrown and propagated higher
 */
//@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport

```

```

        report) throws PhaseException
    {
    }

    /**
     * Executes a step succeeding the main
     *   action.
     *
     * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
     * @param report report on the executed
     *   action (to be filled)
     * @throws PhaseException the exception
     *   can be thrown and propagated higher
     */
    public void postAction(EA ea, PhaseReport
        report) throws PhaseException
    {
        if ((ea.getComputeExecutionTimes() ||
            ea.getComputePhasesExecutionTimes())
            )
        {
            report._stopTime = System.nanoTime();
            report._elapsedTime = ((double) (
                report._stopTime - report.
                _startTime) / 1000000.0);
        }
    }
    [...]
}

```

The following field (“*R*”) holds the (pseudo)random number generator. The generator is a fundamental component of every metaheuristic. Using its poor implementation that does not satisfy expected distributions is a fundamental error. This framework uses by default a 64-bit Mersenne Twister generator – a reliable implementation of a random number generator – delivered by free-to-use libraries from the Apache Software Foundation.

The subsequent two fields: “*populationSize*” and “*offspringSize*” are self-explanatory. They are supposed to represent the number of solutions the algorithm maintains (and keeps between subsequent iterations) and the number of new solutions created in the reproduction step. In most common implementations, these numbers are equal, as delineated in Algorithm 1. However, consider running the method in the steady-state mode for instance (one offspring should be generated in one iteration). If so, the latter field should be set to 1.

The remaining fields are all predefined phases (or their customizations/extensions/etc.) employed in the evolutionary process. Observe that these fields’ allowed values are restricted to be extensions of concrete abstract extensions of the general *AbstractPhase* class (e.g., *AbstractEvaluatePhase* or *AbstractSortPhase*). They will be discussed in later subsections, but the reader is encouraged to review them now. **Important note:** If a phase is not delivered, its execution will be skipped.

Listing 7: EvolutionaryAlgorithm.Params class

```

public static class Params
{
    [...]

    /**
     * Considered criteria.
     */
    public Criteria _criteria;

    /**
     * Random number generator.
     */
    public IRandom _R;

    /**
     * Population size.
     */
    public int _populationSize = 0;

    /**
     * Offspring size.
     */
    public int _offspringSize = 0;

    [...]

    /**
     * "Init starts" phase.
     */
    public AbstractInitStartsPhase
        _initStarts = null;
}

```

2.7. Evolutionary algorithm

The evolutionary algorithm (*ea.EA* class) is founded on predefined phases implemented for JECDM. The evolutionary process it imposes emerges from executing these phases in concrete orders, determining the desired processing and data flow in this way. As with many higher-level classes, parameterization via the inner *Params* class is required to instantiate the object instance.

Listing 7 brings the *ea.EA.Params* class for convenience. Note that, however, it exhibits only the essential fields for the sake of brevity. Nonetheless, all the fields in this class are relatively self-explanatory. It is thus up to the reader to acquaint him/herself with this class.

Consider the criteria field first (the *Criteria* class can be found in the criteria package of the *DecisionSupport* module). It is a wrapper for all criteria (*Criterion* class in the *DecisionSupport* module) considered in the problem tackled by the algorithm (they are stored in the array). It is assumed that one criterion stored in the array is linked to one objective function to be optimized (1:1 index mapping). It holds various objective/criterion-related metadata, e.g., optimization/preference direction or name. **Important note:** This initial release of JECDM primarily concerns criteria that use the ratio scale. The concern of non-ratio scales is in future development plans, and it is assumed that the *Criteria/Criterion* classes will be suitably extended for this purpose.

```

35 /**
   * "Construct initial population" phase.
   */
   public
   AbstractConstructInitialPopulationPhase
       _constructInitialPopulation;

   /**
   * "Assign specimens IDs" phase.
   */
40 public AbstractAssignSpecimenIDs
       _assignSpecimenIDs = new
       AssignSpecimensIDs();

   /**
   * "Evaluate" phase.
   */
45 public AbstractEvaluatePhase _evaluate;

   /**
   * "Sort" phase.
   */
50 public AbstractSortPhase _sort;

   /**
   * "Init ends" phase.
   */
55 public AbstractInitEndsPhase _initEnds =
       null;

   /**
   * "Prepare step" phase.
   */
60 public AbstractPrepareStepPhase
       _prepareStep = null;

   /**
   * "Construct mating pool" phase.
   */
65 public AbstractConstructMatingPoolPhase
       _constructMatingPool = new
       ConstructMatingPool();

   /**
   * "Select parents" phase.
   */
70 public AbstractSelectParentsPhase
       _selectParents;

   /**
   * "Reproduce" phase.
   */
75 public AbstractReproducePhase _reproduce;

   /**
   * "Merge" phase.
   */
80 public AbstractMergePhase _merge = new
       Merge();

   /**

```

```

85 * "Remove" phase.
   */
   public AbstractRemovePhase _remove;

   /**
   * "Finalize step" phase.
   */
90 public AbstractFinalizeStepPhase
       _finalizeStep = new FinalizeStep();

   /**
   * "Update objective space" phase.
   */
95 public AbstractUpdateOSPhase _updateOS =
       null;
}

```

Let us now move to the *EvolutionaryAlgorithm* class itself. Its most relevant code snippets are brought in Listing 8. They showcase the constructor and the primary methods for executing the processing formed from employed phases.

The constructor accepts the params container as input. Its main task is simply setting the field values. Note that all the phases (references) are kept in the array. The predefined phase IDs determine the index under which a phase is stored (see *PhasesIDs* class).

Consider now the “*init*” method. It is supposed to be called just once, at the beginning of the evolutionary process. In JECMDM, the beginning is considered the 0-th generation, which is supposed to be the moment when the initial population is constructed. Note that this procedure sets the “*currentTimestamp*” field to *EATimestamp(0, 0)*. The *EATimestamp* (*ea* package) is a simple immutable class that represents a two-element tuple: (generation; steady-state repeat).

The initialization method is designed to execute the following phases in the provided order:

1. **PHASE_INIT_STARTS:** This step can be implemented to perform some auxiliary operations before executing the rest of the phases. It can be considered the “init of the init” step.
2. **PHASE_CONSTRUCT_INITIAL_POPULATION:** Here, an initial population is supposed to be constructed (but not evaluated).
3. **PHASE_ASSIGN_SPECIMENS_IDS:** This can be considered a “technical” step. The default implementation will assign unique identifiers to the solutions that have just been delivered (based on the current context, e.g., generation).
4. **PHASE_EVALUATE:** The maintained population of solutions can be evaluated in this step.
5. **PHASE_UPDATE_OS:** The objective space manager, discussed in Section 2.5, can update its internal data based on the initial specimens.
6. **PHASE_SORT:** This phase can be employed to execute auxiliary sorting in the maintained population (e.g., to speed up seeking the most promising solutions in the upcoming steps).

7. **PHASE_INIT_ENDS**: This step can be considered a finalizer of the initialization procedure. It can be implemented to perform extra operations.

Important note: The above steps are not hard-coded implementations. One can design each phase individually to serve particular needs (or even turn some off). The initialization step was divided into smaller steps with fixed labels to introduce higher-level interpretability of designed algorithmic components. Names like “evaluate” and “sort” are somewhat familiar and intuitive to any practitioner of evolutionary computation. Nonetheless, some basic (and standard) implementations that help reduce the coding required to develop a new algorithm are provided along with the framework. They will be discussed in the following Section 2.8.

Note that the abovementioned phases are not explicitly executed by calling “*IPhase.perform*” during initialization. Instead, the execution is delegated to the auxiliary “*executePhase*” method (which is brought in Listing 8). This supportive procedure first checks if the requested phase is null. If so, its execution is skipped. Then, it calls the “*IPhase.perform*” method but also handles the returned *PhaseReport* object. In the initial framework’s release, the report is only used to (conditionally; relevant flags must be turned on) update the information on the total time the phase has been running so far (in ms).

Listing 8: EvolutionaryAlgorithm class

```

public class EA
{
    [...]

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor. Sets EA as
     * imposed by the provided params
     * container.
     *
     * @param p params container
     */
    public EA(Params p)
    {
        _name = p._name;
        _criteria = p._criteria;
        _id = p._id;

        _populationSize = p._populationSize;
        _offspringSize = p._offspringSize;

        [...]

        _phases = new IPhase[PhasesIDs.
            _phaseNames.length];
        _phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_INIT_STARTS] =
            p._initStarts;
        _phases[PhasesIDs.
            PHASE_CONSTRUCT_INITIAL_POPULATION]
            = p._constructInitialPopulation;
        _phases[PhasesIDs.
            PHASE_ASSIGN_SPECIMENS_IDS] = p.
            _assignSpecimenIDs;
    }
}

```

```

_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_EVALUATE] = p.
    _evaluate;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_SORT] = p._sort
;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_INIT_ENDS] = p.
    _initEnds;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_PREPARE_STEP] =
    p._prepareStep;
_phases[PhasesIDs.
    PHASE_CONSTRUCT_MATING_POOL] = p.
    _constructMatingPool;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_SELECT_PARENTS]
    = p._selectParents;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_REPRODUCE] = p.
    _reproduce;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_MERGE] = p.
    _merge;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_REMOVE] = p.
    _remove;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_UPDATE_OS] = p.
    _updateOS;
_phases[PhasesIDs.PHASE_FINALIZE_STEP]
    = p._finalizeStep;
}

/**
 * Initializes the evolutionary process.
 *
 * @throws EAException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
public void init() throws EAException
{
    startMeasuringTime();
    _currentTimestamp = new EATimestamp(0,
        0);

    executePhase(PhasesIDs.
        PHASE_INIT_STARTS);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.
        PHASE_CONSTRUCT_INITIAL_POPULATION);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.
        PHASE_ASSIGN_SPECIMENS_IDS);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_EVALUATE);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_UPDATE_OS)
        ;
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_SORT);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_INIT_ENDS)
        ;

    stopMeasuringTime();
}

/**
 * Conditionally performs indicated phase
 * (condition = phase is not null)
 *
 * @param phaseID id of the phase to be
 * performed
 * @throws EAException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */

```

```

65  */
private void executePhase(int phaseID)
    throws EAException
{
    if (_phases[phaseID] != null)
    {
70      try
      {
          PhaseReport report = _phases[
              phaseID].perform(this);
          if (report._elapsedTime != null)
              updatePhasesTotalExecutionTimes (
                  report._elapsedTime, phaseID);
75      } catch (PhaseException e)
      {
          throw new EAException("Error
              occurred when executing phase =
              " + _phases[phaseID].getName() +
              " " + e.
              getDetailedReasonMessage(), this
              .getClass(), e);
      }
    }
80 }

/**
 * Executes one step of the evolutionary
    algorithm.
85  *
 * @param timestamp generation; steady-
    state repeat
 * @throws EAException the exception can
    be thrown and propagated higher
 */
public void step(EATimestamp timestamp)
    throws EAException
90 {
    startMeasuringTime();
    _currentTimestamp = timestamp;

    executePhase(PhasesIDs.
        PHASE_PREPARE_STEP);
95    executePhase(PhasesIDs.
        PHASE_CONSTRUCT_MATING_POOL);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.
        PHASE_SELECT_PARENTS);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_REPRODUCE)
        ;
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.
        PHASE_ASSIGN_SPECIMENS_IDS);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_EVALUATE);
100    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_MERGE);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_UPDATE_OS)
        ;
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_SORT);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.PHASE_REMOVE);
    executePhase(PhasesIDs.
        PHASE_FINALIZE_STEP);
105
    stopMeasuringTime();
}

```

```

110 }

```

Consider now the method “step” in Listing 8. Its only input is the current timestamp (*EATimestamp*), which is immediately stored as the current timestamp. Note that the evolutionary method is not supposed to trigger the execution of the steps itself. Instead, it should be handled by the already mentioned runner object (*runner.IRunner*), which is also responsible for ensuring that the provided timestamps will be consistently increasing (e.g., by one generation). Noticeable, the step is divided into the following phases:

1. **PHASE_PREPARE_STEP:** Similar to “*PHASE_INIT_STARTS*,” this phase can be considered the “init of the step.” It can be implemented to perform some auxiliary operations.
2. **PHASE_CONSTRUCT_MATING_POOL:** This phase can be implemented to establish a mating pool (field of *SpecimenContainer*). A mating pool consists of solutions allowed to become parent ones. By default, the whole current population is considered a mating pool. However, some well-known algorithms use the concept of a restricted mating pool, e.g., MOEA/D [6].
3. **PHASE_SELECT_PARENTS:** Parent selection can be executed in this phase. The parents can be stored in the *SpecimenContainer*.
4. **PHASE_REPRODUCE:** Next, selected parents can be reproduced to construct offspring, which can be saved in the *SpecimenContainer*.
5. **PHASE_ASSIGN_SPECIMENS_IDS:** The newly constructed specimens can be assigned IDs in this phase.
6. **PHASE_EVALUATE:** After the offspring specimens are assigned IDs, they can be evaluated.
7. **PHASE_UPDATE_OS:** This phase is dedicated to updating the objective space manager (determines the bounds for the objective space) using the current population.
8. **PHASE_MERGE:** This phase can be implemented to, e.g., merge the current population with the offspring.
9. **PHASE_SORT:** This phase is intended to sort population members.
10. **PHASE_REMOVE:** This phase can be implemented to remove the excess of the least satisfactory solutions.
11. **PHASE_FINALIZE_STEP:** Finally, this phase can be implemented to perform some auxiliary procedures that should be executed during step finalization.

2.8. Default implementations of phases

This section overviews the default phases implemented for the initial release of the JECM. They were intended to cover most of the functionalities related to the flow of typical evolutionary algorithm implementations. Even with this, the programmer may adapt them (overwrite) to serve expected needs (or not use them at all). The following sections briefly discuss the default phases provided. Note that the included code snippets are focused mainly on the “action” method of the “*AbstractPhase*” class, which is overwritten by the default phases.

2.8.1. Initialization starts (PHASE_INIT_STARTS)

No “init phase” considered general or universal is provided. However, various concrete implementations, e.g., of the preference-based methods, have dedicated implementations of this phase, but they will be discussed later.

2.8.2. Construct initial population (PHASE_CONSTRUCT_INITIAL_POPULATION)

Default class: *phase.ConstructInitialPopulation*

Listing 9 brings the “action” method of the default implementation. The code is self-explanatory. First, an array of specimens is created by an auxiliary object implementing the *phase.IConstruct* interface (see Listing 10). Next, the specimen container object (with the array passed via the constructor as the current population) is created and stored in the evolutionary algorithm (the algorithm does not create it itself). Finally, the phase sets the “population requires evaluation” and “population requires ID assignment” flags to *true* to indicate that the created specimens have not been evaluated nor their IDs have been assigned yet. Note that it is implicitly assumed that the array returned by the *IConstruct* object will be of a size equal to the “population size” field stored by *ea.EA* (but it does not have to be; it is implementation-dependent; the programmer must ensure that the flow is consistent and error-free).

Notably, the actual specimen creation is delegated to an auxiliary object implementing the *phase.IConstruct* interface. This way, one may supply their implementation of this interface and use it along with the default phase implementation if (s)he is happy with how it establishes the processing.

Listing 9: ConstructInitialPopulation class (action method)

```
/**
 * Phase main action. Creates the initial
 * population.
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
 * as follows:
 * - The method delegates the construction
 * of specimens to {@link IConstruct}.
 * - The created specimen array will be
 * stored in {@link population}.
 * SpecimensContainer#setPopulation(
 * ArrayList)}
 * (accessible via {@link EA#
 * getSpecimensContainer()}).
 * - The action method sets the {@link
 * SpecimensContainer#
 * setPopulationRequiresEvaluation(boolean
 * )} and
 * {@link SpecimensContainer#
 * setPopulationRequiresIDAssignment(
 * boolean)} flags to true.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 * action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
```

```
*/
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
report) throws PhaseException
{
    ArrayList<Specimen> specimen =
        _constructor.createInitialPopulation(
            ea);
    ea.setSpecimensContainer(new
        SpecimensContainer(specimen));
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setPopulationRequiresEvaluation(true);
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setPopulationRequiresIDAssignment(true
        );
}
```

Listing 10: IConstruct interface

```
/**
 * Creates initial population (array of
 * specimens).
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
 * as follows:
 * - The method is supposed to create a
 * specimen array of size {@link EA#
 * getPopulationSize()}.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @return specimen array
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
ArrayList<Specimen> createInitialPopulation
(EA ea) throws PhaseException;
```

2.8.3. Assign specimens IDs (PHASE_ASSIGN_SPECIMENS_IDS)

Default class: *phase.AssignSpecimensIDs*

The default implementation of a phase responsible for assigning IDs to newly constructed specimens is common for the initialization of an evolutionary algorithm and its step method. Its most relevant code snippets are brought in Listing 11. The implementation is straightforward. The action method checks the “population/offspring requires ID assignment” flags and conditionally delegates the ID assignment (applied to a respective specimen array) to the auxiliary method “assignIDs.”

Listing 11: AssignSpecimensIDs class (the most relevant methods)

```
/**
 * Phase’s main action. Assigns IDs to
 * specimens. The ID (for a specimen) is
 * constructed using its in-array index,
 * the EA id ({@link EA#getID()}), current
 * generation ({@link EA#
 * getCurrentGeneration()}), and current
 * steady-state
```

```

* repeat ({@link EA#
  getCurrentSteadyStateRepeat()}). The
  specimens stored in {@link
  SpecimensContainer#getPopulation()}
5 * and/or {@link SpecimensContainer#
  getOffspring()} are assigned IDs (
  depends on the {@link
  SpecimensContainer#
  isPopulationRequiringIDAssignment()})
* and {@link SpecimensContainer#
  isOffspringRequiringIDAssignment()})
  flags).
*
* @param ea evolutionary algorithm
* @param report report on the executed
  action (to be filled)
10 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
  be thrown and propagated higher
*/
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
  report) throws PhaseException
{
15   if (ea.getSpecimensContainer().
    isPopulationRequiringIDAssignment())
    assignIDs(ea, ea.
      getSpecimensContainer().
      getPopulation());
   if (ea.getSpecimensContainer().
    isOffspringRequiringIDAssignment())
    assignIDs(ea, ea.
      getSpecimensContainer().
      getOffspring());
}
20 /**
 * Auxiliary method. Instantiates specimens
  IDs.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param specimens array of specimens to
  be assigned ID
 */
private void assignIDs(EA ea, ArrayList<
  Specimen> specimens)
{
30   for (int i = 0; i < specimens.size(); i
    ++)
   {
    specimens.get(i).setID(new SpecimenID(
      ea.getID(), ea.getCurrentGeneration
      (), ea.getCurrentSteadyStateRepeat()
      , i));
   }
}

```

2.8.4. Evaluate (PHASE_EVALUATE)

Default class: *phase.Evaluate*

As with the previous phases, the default implementation of the

“evaluate” phase follows a similar delegation pattern. Specifically, the action method (see Listing 12) conditionally delegates the evaluation of the current population (typically required during the initialization) or the offspring (required in the following iterations) to an auxiliary object implementing a *phase.IEvaluate* interface (see Listing 13). It is implicitly assumed that the specimens’ evaluation vectors will be stored in their “performance” vectors (*Alternative* class).

Listing 12: Evaluate class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action (evaluates specimens).
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
  as follows:
 * - The method delegates the evaluation of
  specimens stored in {@link
  SpecimensContainer#getPopulation()} and
  /or
5 * {@link SpecimensContainer#getOffspring()
  } (depends on the {@link
  SpecimensContainer#
  isPopulationRequiringEvaluation()})
 * and {@link SpecimensContainer#
  isOffspringRequiringEvaluation()}) flags
  ) to {@link IEvaluate}.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
  action (to be filled)
10 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
  be thrown and propagated higher
*/
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
  report) throws PhaseException
{
15   if (ea.getSpecimensContainer().
    isPopulationRequiringEvaluation())
    _evaluate.evaluateSpecimens(ea.
      getSpecimensContainer().
      getPopulation());
   if (ea.getSpecimensContainer().
    isOffspringRequiringEvaluation())
    _evaluate.evaluateSpecimens(ea.
      getSpecimensContainer().getOffspring
      ());
}

```

Listing 13: IEvaluate interface

```

/**
 * Evaluates specimens.
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
  as follows:
 * - the evaluation result for each
  specimen will be stored as {@link
  Specimen#setEvaluations(double[])})
 * (see {@link Alternative#getPerformance()
  }); when it comes to some auxiliary
  scores: in
5

```

```

10 * {@link Specimen#setAuxScore(double)};
    see {@link Alternative#getAuxScores()}.
    *
    * @param specimens array of specimens to
    be evaluated
    * @throws PhaseException the exception can
    be thrown and propagated higher
    */
void evaluateSpecimens (ArrayList<Specimen>
    specimens) throws PhaseException;

```

2.8.5. Sort (PHASE_SORT)

Default class: *phase.SortByPerformanceValue*

One can use this implementation of the *AbstractSortPhase* class to sort population members according to their performance (stored in the performance vector at 0 index; see the *Alternative* class). The code is brought in Listing 14. Alternatively, another default implementation is provided: *SortByAuxValue*, which does the same, but the specimens are sorted according to their first (index of 0) auxiliary values.

Listing 14: SortByPerformanceValue class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action (sorts the specimens
 * stored in {@link SpecimensContainer#
 * getPopulation()} by first performance
 * values).
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 * action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
{
    sort.Sort.sortByPerformanceValue(ea.
        getSpecimensContainer().getPopulation
        (), _ascendingOrder);
}

```

2.8.6. Initialization ends (PHASE_INIT_ENDS)

Default class: *phase.InitEnds*

The predefined phase implementation turns off all the “population/offspring requires evaluation/ID assignment” flags (see Listing 15).

Listing 15: InitEnds class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action (sets the “requires
 * evaluation/ID assignment” flags to
 * false).

```

```

*
* @param ea evolutionary algorithm
* @param report report on the executed
* action (to be filled)
* @throws PhaseException the exception can
* be thrown and propagated higher
*/
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
{
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setPopulationRequiresEvaluation(false)
        ;
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setOffspringRequiresEvaluation(false);
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setPopulationRequiresIDAssignment(
        false);
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setOffspringRequiresIDAssignment(false)
        );
}

```

2.8.7. Prepare step (PREPARE_STEP)

As with “PHASE_INIT_STARTS”, the *AbstractPrepareStepPhase* class has no default implementation. However, some algorithm-specific implementations have been delivered in JECDM, but they will be discussed later.

2.8.8. Construct *mating* *pool* (PHASE_CONSTRUCT_MATING_POOL)

Default class: *phase.ConstructMatingPool*

The default implementation of this phase explicitly treats the current population array as the mating pool (see the Listing 16).

Listing 16: ConstructMatingPool class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action. Creates the mating
 * pool.
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
 * as follows:
 * - The population stored in {@link
 * SpecimensContainer#getPopulation()} is
 * considered a mating pool.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 * action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
{

```

```

ea.getSpecimensContainer().setMatingPool(
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
    getPopulation());
}

```

2.8.9. Select parents (PHASE_SELECT_PARENTS)

Default class: *phase.SelectParents*

The predefined functional block responsible for selecting parents delegates these tasks to an auxiliary object implementing the *selection.ISelect* interface, assuming that the parents are selected from the current mating pool (see Listing 17; the random number generator is supplied by the evolutionary algorithm; **Important note:** The method’s signature is changed in newer versions of JECDM. It now comprises one input: the reference to the EA itself; thus giving great flexibility in creating custom implementations). This supportive object is assumed to return an array of parents (*population.Parents* class; see Listing 18). The selection procedures in the initial framework’s release are random and tournament (see the *selection* package). Note that it is implicitly assumed that the size of the constructed parents array (i.e., the number of *Parents* object to construct) equals the “offspring size” field in *ea.EA* (i.e., one *Parents* object should be constructed per one expected offspring).

Listing 17: ISelect interface

```

/**
 * Constructs array of parents (one element
 *   for one offspring to generate).
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
 *   as follows:
 * - The number of parents to construct ({
 *   @link Parents}) equals the offspring
 *   size ({@link EA#getOffspringSize()}).
 * - The parents are selected from the
 *   passed specimen array (mating pool).
 *
 * @param matingPool mating pool
 * @param R random number generator
 * @return selected parents
 */
ArrayList<Parents> selectParents(ArrayList<
    Specimen> matingPool, IRandom R);

```

Listing 18: SelectParents class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action.
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
 *   as follows:
 * - The selection is delegated to {@link
 *   ISelect}.
 * - The specimens will be selected from
 *   the ones contained in {@link
 *   SpecimensContainer#getMatingPool()}.
 * - The parents will be stored as {@link
 *   SpecimensContainer#setParents(ArrayList
 *   )}.

```

```

*
* @param ea evolutionary algorithm
* @param report report on the executed
*   action (to be filled)
* @throws PhaseException the exception can
*   be thrown and propagated higher
*/
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
{
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().setParents(
        _select.selectParents(ea.
            getSpecimensContainer().getMatingPool
            (), ea.getR()));
}

```

2.8.10. Reproduce (PHASE_REPRODUCE)

Default class: *phase.Reproduce*

This phase’s default implementation also uses a delegation pattern (see Listing 19). Specifically, it passes the construction of an offspring array to an auxiliary object implementing *reproduction.IReproduce* interface (see Listing 20). Similar to the predefined phases already discussed, the API does not impose very strong contracts here. Instead, a general *ea.EA* object is passed as an input. Generally, there are two implicit assumptions in this implementation (that can be violated when required: implementation-dependent). First, the offspring should be constructed from the *Parents* objects stored in the specimen container. Second, the number of offspring specimens returned (array size) should equal the “offspring size” field stored in *ea.EA* (and the number of *Parents* objects stored in the specimen container).

After the offspring array is retrieved, the default implementation sets the “offspring requires evaluation/ID assignment” flags to *true*.

Listing 19: Reproduce class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action.
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
 *   as follows:
 * - Offspring creation is delegated to {
 *   @link IReproduce}.
 * - The number of offspring to create
 *   equals the offspring size {@link EA#
 *   getOffspringSize()}.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 *   action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 *   be thrown and propagated higher
*/
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException

```

```

{
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().setOffspring(
        _reproduce.createOffspring(ea));
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setOffspringRequiresEvaluation(true);
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setOffspringRequiresIDAssignment(true)
        ;
}

```

Listing 20: IReproduce interface

```

/**
 * Creates an array of offspring specimens.
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
 * as follows:
 * - The number of offspring to create
 * equals the offspring size {@link EA#
 * getOffspringSize()}.
 * - One offspring is created using one
 * parents object ({@link population.
 * Parents}) stored in {@link
 * SpecimensContainer#getParents()}.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @return offspring specimens
 */
ArrayList<Specimen> createOffspring(EA ea);

```

2.8.11. Merge (PHASE_MERGE)

Default class: *phase.Merge*

This simple predefined implementation appends the offspring to the current population stored in the specimen container (see Listing 21).

Listing 21: Merge class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action (merges offspring and
 * population).
 * The default (implicit) assumptions are
 * as follows:
 * - It adds the specimens stored in {@link
 * SpecimensContainer#getOffspring()} to
 * the ones stored in
 * {@link SpecimensContainer#getPopulation
 * ()} (see {@link SpecimensContainer#
 * mergeOffspringAndPopulation()}).
 * - Merged population size will equal
 * population size + offspring size.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 * action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException

```

```

{
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        mergeOffspringAndPopulation();
}

```

2.8.12. Update objective space (PHASE_UPDATE_OBJECTIVE_SPACE)

Default class: *phase.UpdateObjectiveSpace*

The default implementation of this phase calls for the “update” method of the objective space manager (see Listing 22). The specimen container object is passed as the primary input. The manager can be customized to indicate which specimens (e.g., offspring) will contribute to the update procedure.

Listing 22: UpdateObjectiveSpace class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action. Delegates the update
 * to {@link ObjectiveSpaceManager}.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 * action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
{
    _osManager.update(ea.
        getSpecimensContainer(), new
        EATimestamp(ea.getCurrentGeneration(),
            ea.getCurrentSteadyStateRepeat()));
}

```

2.8.13. Remove (REMOVE_PHASE)

Default class: *phase.Remove*

The predefined implementation of the *AbstractRemovePhase* truncates the population so that only “population size” (*ea.EA*) of the first stored specimens are preserved (see Listing 23).

Listing 23: Remove class (action method)

```

/**
 * Phase main action (preserves ‘‘
 * population size’’ first specimens
 * stored in the population array; new
 * population array
 * is constructed in this process).
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 * action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher

```

```

10  */
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
15  {
    ArrayList<Specimen> survivalists = new
        ArrayList<>(ea.getPopulationSize());
    for (int i = 0; i < ea.getPopulationSize
        (); i++) survivalists.add(ea.
        getSpecimensContainer().getPopulation
        ().get(i));
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().setPopulation(
        survivalists);
}

```

2.8.14. Finalize step

Default class: *phase.Finalize*

The default implementation of the “finalize step” phase resets the “population/offspring requires evaluation/ID assignment” flags (see Listing 24).

Listing 24: FinalizeStep class

```

/**
 * Phase main action (sets the “requires
 *   evaluation/ID assignments” flags to
 *   false).
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 *   action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 *   be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
10  {
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setPopulationRequiresEvaluation(false)
        ;
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setOffspringRequiresEvaluation(false);
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setPopulationRequiresIDAssignment(
        false);
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setOffspringRequiresIDAssignment(false)
15  );
}

```

2.9. Summary of default phases and imposed flow

Figure 3 illustrates the flow imposed by the default phases introduced in Section 2.2. It is a helpful handout that can be utilized when developing new methods. Note that the overall flow well-aligns with the basic scheme of an evolutionary method presented in Algorithm 1.

2.10. Bundle classes

The phases are small functional blocks that, when combined and organized, can constitute an evolutionary process. Naturally, parameterizing them all whenever an algorithm is instantiated would be tiresome. This issue has been addressed by introducing hierarchical container-like bundle classes. They allow for designing quick initialization and parameterization paths, which ultimately help to pack various components into an overall algorithmic product. There are three bundle classes:

- *phase.PhasesBundle*,
- *ea.AbstractEABundle*,
- *problem.AbstractProblemBundle*.

Their dependencies/hierarchy are depicted in a simple scheme provided in Figure 4, and they will be discussed in the following sections.

2.10.1. Phases bundle

The *phases.PhasesBundle* class is a straightforward container-like class that encapsulates all phases an evolutionary algorithm uses. It is employed by the *AbstractEABundle* class to store all phases (see the scheme in Figure 4). The class is presented in Listing 25 for convenience. Since the code is plain, it does not require further elaboration. Note that it introduces a supportive method “*copyPhasesFromBundleToEA*” that can be called to fill the params container of an evolutionary algorithm as imposed by the phases bundle object.

Listing 25: PhasesBundle class

```

/**
 * Used to store phases and pass between
 *   different objects.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class PhasesBundle
5  {
    /**
     * "Init starts" phase.
     */
    public AbstractInitStartsPhase
        _initStarts;
10
    /**
     * "Construct initial population" phase.
     */
    public
        AbstractConstructInitialPopulationPhase
        _constructInitialPopulation;
15
    /**
     * "Assign Specimens IDs" phase.
     */
    public AbstractAssignSpecimenIDs
        _assignSpecimenIDs = new
        AssignSpecimensIDs();
20
}

```


Figure 3: Basic scheme of the flow imposed by the predefined phases used by an evolutionary algorithm

Figure 4: Dependencies/hierarchy of the bundle-classes

```

25 /**
   * "Evaluate" phase.
   */
   public AbstractEvaluatePhase _evaluate;

30 /**
   * "Sort" phase.
   */
   public AbstractSortPhase _sort;

35 /**
   * "Init ends" phase.
   */
   public AbstractInitEndsPhase _initEnds =
       new InitEnds();

40 /**
   * "Prepare step" phase.
   */
   public AbstractPrepareStepPhase
       _prepareStep = null;

45 /**
   * "Construct mating pool" phase.
   */
   public AbstractConstructMatingPoolPhase
       _constructMatingPool = new
       ConstructMatingPool();

50 /**
   * "Select parents" phase.
   */
   public AbstractSelectParentsPhase
       _selectParents;

55 /**
   * "Reproduce" phase.
   */
   public AbstractReproducePhase _reproduce;

60 /**
   * "Merge" phase.
   */
   public AbstractMergePhase _merge = new
       Merge();

   /**
   * "Remove" phase.

```

```

65 */
   public AbstractRemovePhase _remove;

70 /**
   * "Finalize step" phase.
   */
   public AbstractFinalizeStepPhase
       _finalizeStep = new FinalizeStep();

75 /**
   * "Update objective space" phase.
   */
   public AbstractUpdateOSPhase _updateOS =
       null;

80 /**
   * Supportive method that sets phases in
   * {@link EA.Params} as imposed by the
   * bundle object.
   *
   * @param p {@link EA.Params} object to
   * be passed to EA's constructor
   * @param B instantiated phases
   */
   public static void
       copyPhasesFromBundleToEA(EA.Params p,
       PhasesBundle B)
   {
85     p._initStarts = B._initStarts;
       p._constructInitialPopulation = B.
           _constructInitialPopulation;
       p._assignSpecimenIDs = B.
           _assignSpecimenIDs;
       p._evaluate = B._evaluate;
90     p._sort = B._sort;
       p._initEnds = B._initEnds;
       p._prepareStep = B._prepareStep;
       p._constructMatingPool = B.
           _constructMatingPool;
       p._selectParents = B._selectParents;
95     p._reproduce = B._reproduce;
       p._merge = B._merge;
       p._remove = B._remove;
       p._finalizeStep = B._finalizeStep;
       p._updateOS = B._updateOS;
100 }
   }

```

2.10.2. Abstract EA bundle

The *AbstractEABundle* class is a top-level container-like class that assists in developing concrete algorithms, e.g., NSGA-II [3] or MOEA/D [6]. For this reason, the class can be extended (e.g., “*MyAlgorithmBundle extends AbstractEABundle*”), and its auxiliary methods can be suitably overwritten. Furthermore, the parameterization path can be suitably introduced by, e.g., defining – in the extending class – dedicated constructors, factory-like static methods, or extending the params container.

The *AbstractEABundle* is brought in Listing 26 for convenience. Consider first its params container. Notably, it does not

involve any field that is a phase. The closest to this are the four auxiliary interfaces: *IConstruct*, *IReproduce*, *IEvaluate*, and *ISelect*. The reason is that the bundle intends to hide the explicit provision of phases. Instead, a reasonably designed bundle should focus on passing the parameters for pre-fixed phases. Note that the params container has one method that can be extended to instantiate default field values (“*instantiateDefaultValues*”; it is called by the bundle constructor). Additionally, these four auxiliary interfaces are not explicitly related to algorithm definition per se but rather to the tackled problem and its solution (assumed solution representation, employed objective function, etc.).

Let’s focus now on the protected constructor. It calls multiple “instantiate”-methods, each referring to a different phase (e.g., “*InstantiateInitStartsPhase()*”). These methods are passed the params container and are intended to be overwritten when designing an algorithm-dedicated bundle to explicitly specify which phases’ implementations should be used.

Note that this section provides a brief overview of this class. Further sections that will be example-oriented will discuss how this class can be used in practice.

Listing 26: AbstractEABundle class

```

/**
 * Abstract class supporting the
 * parameterization of EA.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public abstract class AbstractEABundle
{
    /**
     * Params container.
     */
    public static class Params
    {
        /**
         * Name of the EA.
         */
        public String _name = null;

        /**
         * Considered criteria.
         */
        public Criteria _criteria;

        /**
         * Constructs initial specimens.
         */
        public IConstruct _construct;

        /**
         * Constructs offspring.
         */
        public IReproduce _reproduce;

        /**
         * Evaluates new solutions.
         */
        public IEvaluate _evaluate;
    }

    /**
     * Parents selection procedure.
     */
    public ISelect _select;

    [...]

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param name      name of the EA
     * @param criteria  criteria used to
     *                  assess population members
     */
    public Params(String name, Criteria
                  criteria)
    {
        _name = name;
        _criteria = criteria;
    }

    [...]

    /**
     * Auxiliary method called by the
     * constructor at the beginning to
     * instantiate default params values (
     * optional).
     */
    protected void instantiateDefaultValues
    (
    )
    {

    }

    /**
     * Name of the EA.
     */
    public String _name;

    /**
     * Phases bundle.
     */
    public PhasesBundle _phasesBundle;

    /**
     * Reference to the objective space
     * manager.
     */
    public ObjectiveSpaceManager _osManager;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param p params container
     */
    public AbstractEABundle(Params p)
    {
        p.instantiateDefaultValues();
    }
}

```

```

    _name = p._name;
    _phasesBundle = new PhasesBundle();
    _osManager = p._osManager;
95  instantiateInitStartsPhase(p);
    instantiateConstructInitialPopulation
        Phase(p);
    instantiateAssignSpecimensIDPhase(p);
    instantiateEvaluatePhase(p);
100  instantiateSortPhase(p);
    instantiateInitEndsPhase(p);
    instantiatePrepareStepPhase(p);
    instantiateConstructMatingPoolPhase(p);
    instantiateSelectParentsPhase(p);
    instantiateReproducePhase(p);
105  instantiateMergePhase(p);
    instantiateRemovePhase(p);
    instantiateFinalizeStepPhase(p);
    instantiateUpdateObjectiveSpacePhase(p)
        ;
    registerOSChangeListeners(p);
110  registerInitialNormalizations(p);
}

/**
 * Auxiliary method instantiating the "
 *   init starts" phase.
 *
 * @param p params container
 */
protected void instantiateInitStartsPhase
    (Params p)
{
120  _phasesBundle._initStarts = null;
}

/**
 * Auxiliary method instantiating the "
 *   create initial population" phase.
 *
 * @param p params container
 */
protected void
    instantiateConstructInitialPopulation
    Phase(Params p)
{
130  _phasesBundle.
        _constructInitialPopulation = null;
    if (p._construct != null)
        _phasesBundle.
            _constructInitialPopulation = new
                ConstructInitialPopulation(p.
                    _construct);
}
135  [...]
}

```

2.10.3. Problem bundle

While the *AbstractEABundle* class is algorithm-oriented, the *AbstractProblemBundle* class focuses on the problem to solve. Nonetheless, the problem and the algorithm are interrelated as,

e.g., the problem's objective function can explicitly (or implicitly) dictate how to evaluate solutions in the population – and the evaluation is one of the steps of the algorithm.

The *AbstractProblemBundle* class is provided in Listing 27. Notably, it has four fields that can be passed via the protected constructor: a problem identifier (see the *problem.Problem* class), an *IConstruct* object, an *IReproduce* object, and an *IEvaluate* object. Note that these objects should be designed consistently, e.g., assume the exact solution representation. As shown in the scheme in Figure 4, the parameterized problem instance can be coupled with the algorithm bundle to obtain a final parameterization of an algorithm tuned for solving a specified optimization problem.

In the initial release of JECDM, two problem bundles are delivered: DTLZ [4] (see *problem.moo.dtlz.DTLZBundle*), WFG [5] (see *problem.moo.wfg.WFGBundle*). These are well-known test suites in multi-objective optimization (and will be discussed more extensively in “*Tutorial 3: Evolutionary Computation module – part 2: multi-objective optimization*” document).

Listing 27: AbstractProblemBundle class

```

/**
 * Abstract bundle (container) for default
 *   implementations for solving various
 *   problems (construct/reproduce/evaluate,
 *   etc.).
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
5 public abstract class AbstractProblemBundle
{
    /**
     * Problem ID.
     */
    10 public final Problem _problem;

    /**
     * Constructs initial population.
     */
    15 public final IConstruct _construct;

    /**
     * Creates offspring.
     */
    20 public final IReproduce _reproduce;

    /**
     * Evaluates solutions.
     */
    25 public final IEvaluate _evaluate;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param problem problem id
     * @param construct constructs the
     *   initial population
     * @param reproduce creates offspring
     * @param evaluate Evaluates solutions

```

```

35  */
protected AbstractProblemBundle(Problem
    problem, IConstruct construct,
    IReproduce reproduce, IEvaluate
    evaluate)
{
    _problem = problem;
    _construct = construct;
40  _reproduce = reproduce;
    _evaluate = evaluate;
}

[...]

45  /**
    * Checks if a problem is a DTLZ problem
    *
    * @param problem problem id
50  * @return true = the problem is a DTLZ
    *         problem; false otherwise
    */
public static boolean isDTLZ(Problem
    problem)
{
    return (problem.equals(Problem.DTLZ1))
        ||
55  (problem.equals(Problem.DTLZ2)) ||
        (problem.equals(Problem.DTLZ3)) ||
        (problem.equals(Problem.DTLZ4)) ||
        (problem.equals(Problem.DTLZ5)) ||
        (problem.equals(Problem.DTLZ6)) ||
60  (problem.equals(Problem.DTLZ7));
}

[...]
}

```

2.11. Runner

As shown in Section 2.1, the *Runner* (*runner* package) class is the highest in the three-level hierarchy. It is responsible for correctly executing the evolutionary processes(es) designed in the implemented evolutionary algorithms (*ea.EA*). The initial release of JECDM introduces three sources: the interface *runner.IRunner* that sets the contracts, the *AbstractRunner* class (implements the *IRunner*) that implements most of the functionalities, and a straightforward, accessible extension of the abstract class: *Runner*. This split was done to allow the implementation of new, consistent runner objects in the future.

The default implementation of the runner interface is primarily responsible for:

- correctly executing the “*init*” and “*steps*” methods on the evolutionary algorithms handled (hence, changing their states);
- coupling the evolutionary processes with the visualization module (will be discussed in Section 2.11.1).

The runner was implemented not only to execute evolutionary processes manually but was primarily designed to allow

the automatization of this task in the *Experimentation* module. In this way, the *IRunner* bridges the *EvolutionaryComputation* and *Experimentation* modules.

Now, let us focus on the concept of iteration in JECDM. As already explained, iteration in JECDM is a two-element tuple comprising a current generation and steady-state repeat numbers. The generation is assumed to be the primary timestamp, where the steady-state repeat is subtier. In other words, the generation is considered an iteration in JECDM, while the steady-state repeats a “sub-iteration”. Therefore, both levels can be understood as two nested loops, where the external one iterates over generation numbers, while the internal over steady-state repeats. **Important note:** it is assumed that the iteration over sub-iterations cannot be explicitly interrupted, e.g., to make some measurements (the exception is the coupled visualization module, which can use the intermediate results). However, it can be done between subsequent iterations.

Algorithm 2 A general scheme of executing evolutionary processes imposed by the *AbstractRunner* class.

Input: *EAs* – evolutionary algorithms; *GEN[ea]* – generation limit for an evolutionary algorithm (*ea*); *SSR[ea]* – steady-state repeats for an evolutionary algorithm (*ea*).

```

1: for ea ∈ EAs do
2:   ea.init()
3: for gen = 1, ..., max{GEN} – 1 do
4:   for ea ∈ EAs do
5:     if gen ≥ GEN[ea] then continue
6:     for ssr = 0, ..., SSR[ea] – 1 do
7:       ea.step(gen, ssr)

```

The overall iteration process imposed by the runner is presented (and simplified) in Algorithm 2 for convenience. First, the Runner can handle multiple evolutionary algorithms intended to be executed. They are stored in an array. Next, an associated generation limit and the number of steady-state repeats are associated with each algorithm. Usually, the generation limits will often be the same for different methods when performing experiments (to make the comparison fair). However, the number of steady-state repeats is implementation-dependent. For instance, it can be 1 for generational methods (e.g., NSGA-II), effectively resulting in a single iteration in the nested loop. In turn, the steady-state method may require suitably adjusting this number. For instance, the MOEA/D [6] method implemented in this framework assumes that the number of repeats equals the population size, and in each sub-iteration, a different scalar optimization function will be updated.

Algorithm 2 starts by calling the “*init*” method for all evolutionary algorithms (lines 1-2). Note that the first iteration (generation) is assumed to equal 0. Next, the external loop iterates over generation numbers, starting from 1 and ending on *max*{...} – 1 (line 3). The “–1” in the max formula ensures that the total number of generations will equal the expected number; the initialization is also considered a generation).

Within the external loop, the Runner iterates over the evolutionary methods (line 4). Note that all methods are updated

given the iteration, instead of completing the execution of one method before starting another, to allow simultaneous observation of the performance of all algorithms (and taking measurements). However, the generation can be skipped for a particular evolutionary method if its limit for the number of generations has been exceeded (line 5). Lines 5-6 are devoted to the inner loop, where the “step” procedure is called, using a timestamp composed of the current generation and steady-state repeats numbers (notably, each method may have its own specified limit for the inner loop).

Listing 28: IRunner interface

```

/**
 * Interface for classes responsible for
 *   executing EAs.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface IRunner
{
    /**
     * Initializes EAs. Default
     *   implementation: the method runs pre,
     *   main, and post-init phases (in the
     *   given order).
     *
     * @throws RunnerException exception can
     *   be captured when executing the
     *   evolutionary algorithm and propagated
     *   higher
     */
    void init() throws RunnerException;

    /**
     * Executes the evolution (from scratch,
     *   i.e., calls inits etc.) for the
     *   specified number of generations.
     *
     * @param generations specified number of
     *   generations (the same for each
     *   evolutionary algorithm)
     *
     * @throws RunnerException exception can
     *   be captured when executing the
     *   evolutionary algorithm and propagated
     *   higher
     */
    void executeEvolution(int generations)
        throws RunnerException;

    /**
     * Executes the evolution (from scratch,
     *   i.e., calls inits etc.) for the
     *   specified number of generations.
     *
     * @param generations specified number of
     *   generations; each element
     *   corresponds to a different
     *   evolutionary algorithm
     *
     * (1:1) mapping; hence, the array length
     * should equal the number of algorithms
     */
    void executeEvolution(int[] generations)
        throws RunnerException;

    /**
     * Performs a single generation of EAs.
     *   Default implementation: the method
     *   runs pre, main, and post init phases
     *   (in the given order).
     *
     * @param generation current generation
     *   number
     * @param generationLimits limits for the
     *   number of generations an EA is
     *   allowed run (one element per each EA,
     *   1:1 mapping;
     *
     * note that the generation counter
     * starts from 0);
     *
     * this field excludes those EAs who have
     * reached their generation limit;
     *
     * can be null -> not used
     *
     * @throws RunnerException exception can
     *   be captured when executing the
     *   evolutionary algorithm and propagated
     *   higher
     */
    void executeSingleGeneration(int
        generation, int[] generationLimits)
        throws RunnerException;

    /**
     * Executes a single steady-state repeat
     *   of an EA.
     *
     * Default implementation: the method
     * runs pre, main, and post init phases
     * (in the given order).
     *
     * @param ea evolutionary algorithm whose
     *   single steady-state repeat is to be
     *   executed
     * @param generation current generation
     *   number
     * @param steadyStateRepeat steady-state
     *   repeat number
     *
     * @throws RunnerException exception can
     *   be captured when executing the
     *   evolutionary algorithm and propagated
     *   higher
     */
    void executeSingleSteadyStateRepeat(EA ea
        , int generation, int
        steadyStateRepeat) throws
        RunnerException;

    /**
     * Stops simulations. Default
     *   implementation: the method runs pre,
     *   main, and post init phases (in the

```

```

        given order).
    *
    * @throws RunnerException exception can
    * be captured when executing the
    * evolutionary algorithm and propagated
    * higher
60 */
void stop() throws RunnerException;

/**
 * Optional method for terminating the
 * execution and clearing data.
65 *
 * @throws RunnerException exception can
 * be captured when executing the
 * evolutionary algorithm and propagated
 * higher
 */
void dispose() throws RunnerException;
}

```

Listing 29: Params class

```

/**
 * Params container.
 */
public static class Params
5 {

    /**
     * Evolutionary algorithm(s).
     */
10 public EA[] _eas;

    /**
     * The number of steady-state iterations.
     * Each element represents the number of
     * steady-state repeats for a different
     * EA (1:1 mapping).
15 * Hence, the array length equals the
     * number of EAs.
     */
    public int[] _steadyStateRepeats;

    /**
20 * Optional object responsible for
     * performing visualization (can be null
     * -> visualization-related
     * functionality is ignored).
     */
    public IVisualization _visualization;

    /**
25 * Display Mode flag (see flags
     * descriptions).
     */
    public DisplayMode _displayMode =
        DisplayMode.AT_THE_END;

    /**
30 * Updaters mode flag (see flags
     * descriptions).

```

```

    */
    public UpdaterMode _updaterMode =
        UpdaterMode.AT_THE_END;

    [...]
}

```

Listing 28 showcases the *IRunner* interface. The listed methods and their descriptions are relatively self-explanatory, but the code was brought here for convenience. However, let us focus now on the params container for the *AbstractRunner* class (see Listing 29; the *AbstractRunner* class per se is also not provided here; the reader is recommended to acquaint themselves with this implementation on their own). The params container has several essential fields that can be set to customize the runner process (note that some supportive constructors are also available).

First, the instances of evolutionary algorithms can be delivered via the “_eas” array. Next, each algorithm can be assigned the number of steady-state repeats to be performed per iteration. These can be provided via the “_steadyStateRepeats” array. It is assumed that *i*-th number corresponds to *i*-th algorithm in the “_eas” array. Note that the generation limit array is not considered a class field. Instead, it is supposed to be delivered by the main execution methods (see the interface in Listing 28).

The remaining three fields are linked to the coupled visualization mode (which will be discussed more extensively in the following section). First, the “_visualization” object that implements *visualization.IVisualization* interface can be delivered to couple the running process with visualization (if null, the visualization is not used).

The following field (“_displayMode”) determines when the visualization window should be opened. There are two flags available: “FROM_THE_BEGINNING” and “AT_THE_END”. The first will force the visualization to start before running the evolutionary processes. Note that a synchronization barrier will be used to ensure that the evolution will begin after the window is opened and made visible (see the *AbstractRunner.init()* implementation). In turn, the latter mode will trigger displaying the results after all methods end their executions (see the *AbstractRunner.stop()* implementation).

Regarding the last field, i.e., “_updaterMode”, it dictates when the rendering data should be updated. There are three modes available, which are self-explanatory: “AT_THE_END”, “AFTER_GENERATION”, and “AFTER_STEADY_STATE_REPEAT”.

2.11.1. On the visualization mode

The runner object can be coupled with the visualization tools (*Visualization* module) to illustrate the progression of employed evolutionary algorithms. To bridge the *EvolutionaryComputation* and *Visualization* modules, an auxiliary *visualization.IVisualization* interface and its direct (and currently the only ones) implementations are introduced (*AbstractVisualization* and *Visualization* classes). The source code of the *IVisualization* interface is brought in Listing 30 for brevity. Its core

method is “*updateData()*”, which is intended to be called any time the rendered data requires an update (e.g., due to progression in evolution). This method, i.e., its implementation in the abstract class, is called by the runner object, provided that the visualization object was supplied via the params container.

Listing 30: IVisualization interface

```

/**
 * Interface for classes responsible for
 * visualizing evolutionary processes.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface IVisualization
{
    /**
     * Triggers data update. The new data is
     * constructed, processed, and
     * accordingly sent to plots,
     * as imposed by {@link updater.
     * DataUpdater}.
     */
    void updateData();

    /**
     * Can be used to check if the window (
     * JFrame) is opened (visible and drawn)
     *
     * @return true = the window (JFrame) is
     * opened (visible and drawn), false
     * otherwise
     */
    boolean isWindowDisplayed();

    /**
     * Supportive method for initialization.
     */
    void init();

    /**
     * Supportive method that displays the
     * main frame.
     */
    void display();

    /**
     * Starts (resumes) awaiting background
     * processes.
     */
    void startBackgroundThreads();

    /**
     * Pauses ongoing background processes.
     */
    void stopBackgroundThreads();

    /**
     * Supportive method that terminates
     * visualization.

```

```

 */
void dispose();
}

```

The default abstract class comprises two essential fields (see Listing 31): the “*Frame _frame*” and “*DataUpdater _dataUpdater*” (both from the *Visualization* module). The first is a displayable container for the plot (or plots), while the latter is responsible for executing the update of the input data for rendering. Both classes were introduced and discussed in the “*Tutorial 1: Visualization Module*” document.

Listing 31: AbstractVisualization class

```

/**
 * Default implementation of {@link
 * IVisualization} for visualizing
 * progression of EAs.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public abstract class AbstractVisualization
    implements IVisualization
{
    /**
     * Main frame wrapping the plots
     */
    protected final Frame _frame;

    /**
     * Data updater (creates/processes/and
     * sends data to be visualized to plots)
     */
    protected final DataUpdater _dataUpdater;

    [...]

    /**
     * Triggers data update. The new data is
     * constructed, processed, and
     * accordingly sent to plots,
     * as imposed by {@link updater.
     * DataUpdater}.
     */
    @Override
    public void updateData()
    {
        if (_dataUpdater != null)
        {
            if (_frame.isTerminating()) return;
            _dataUpdater.update();
        }
    }

    [...]
}

```

As explained in “*Tutorial 1: Visualization Module*”, the data updater must be parameterized with data sources, processors, plots, and suitable associations between these layers. While

the processors and plots are somewhat universal, the source(s) must somehow be associated with an evolutionary method(s). Three general implementations of the *ISource* interface are provided along with the initial release of JECDM to show how such a connection can be achieved.

The first implementation of the *ISource* interface is *visualization.updaters.sources.EASource*. The “*double[][] createData()*” it implements is brought in Listing 32 for convenience. This source must be supplied with the reference to the associated evolutionary algorithm when instantiated. During the data creation, it creates a 2D matrix that aggregates all specimens’ evaluations (the performance vectors are stored in the rows). Thus, this implementation may be convenient when displaying scatterplots illustrating the current population (especially in multi-objective optimization). Additionally, this source can be set to extend the performance vectors stored in the matrix by two additional fields: the current generation and the steady state repeat held by the algorithm). This parameterization may be useful when depicting all populations constructed throughout the evolution and coloring the specimens using a gradient whose color is determined by the specimen’s generation number.

Listing 32: EASource class

```

/**
 * Creates new data and returns it. The
 * data is defined as a 2D matrix: [
 * population members x solutions'
 * evaluations].
 * Additionally, if the _addTimestamp flag
 * is true, the specimens' entries
 * contributing to the final data (double
 * [])
 * are extended will be extended by two
 * additional doubles [generation number,
 * steady-state repeat].
 *
 * @return new data
 */
@Override
public double [][] createData()
{
    ArrayList<Specimen> P =
        getDefaultSpecimens();
    double [][] data = new double [P.size()] [];
    for (int i = 0; i < P.size(); i++)
    {
        if (_addTimestamp)
        {
            double [] e = P.get(i).getEvaluations
                ().clone();
            data[i] = new double[e.length + 2];
            System.arraycopy(e, 0, data[i], 0, e.
                length);
            data[i][e.length] = _ea.
                getCurrentGeneration();
            data[i][e.length + 1] = _ea.
                getCurrentSteadyStateRepeat();
        }
        else data[i] = P.get(i).getEvaluations

```

```

        ().clone();
    }
    return data;
}

```

The second implementation is a *visualization.updaters.sources.GenerationAndStatistics* class (see Listing 33). Its name is suggestive. It constructs a single-data point output that takes the following form: [generation, statistic₁, statistic₂, ..., statistic_s]. The first number can be considered a timestamp. The remaining *s* ones are statistics of specimens’ *i*-th performance value, where *i* is a parameter. The calculations are done using the straightforward *IStatistics* interface, whose implementations are intended to transform a double array into a single, double value (statistic functions are supplied via an array). Overall, this source may be useful when presenting a convergence plot that summarizes specimens maintained by an evolutionary algorithm throughout evolution.

Listing 33: GenerationAndStatistics class

```

/**
 * It creates new data that is defined as:
 * [[generation, statistic1, statistic2
 * ,...statisticN]]. The statistics are
 * derived from the i-th specimen
 * performance values (parameter). This
 * implementation can be useful when
 * generating
 * convergence plots.
 *
 * @return new data
 */
@Override
public double [][] createData()
{
    ArrayList<Specimen> P =
        getDefaultSpecimens();
    double [] sd = new double[P.size()];
    for (int i = 0; i < sd.length; i++) sd[i]
        = P.get(i).getEvaluations()[_index];
    double [] data = new double[1 +
        _statistics.length];
    data[0] = _ea.getCurrentGeneration();
    for (int j = 0; j < _statistics.length; j
        ++
        )
        data[1 + j] = _statistics[j].calculate(sd
            );
    return new double [][]{data};
}

```

The third implementation is *visualization.updaters.sources.GenerationIndicator*. This source is intended to create data in the following form: [[*generation; algorithm’s comprehensive performance (calculated based on the current population)*]] (see Listing 34). The calculation of the performance value is delegated to an auxiliary object that implements an *indicator.IPerformanceIndicator* interface (see Listing 35), which is introduced as the primary interface for various performance indicators implemented to measure the performance of evolutionary algorithms (it is vastly used

in the *Experimentation* module). This source is convenient when depicting the convergence plots that represent the comprehensive performance of an algorithm across generations (e.g., hypervolume attained by an evolutionary multi-objective optimization algorithm).

Listing 34: GenerationIndicator class

```

/**
 * Creates new data and returns it. The
 * data is defined as: [[generation,
 * indicator value]]. The indicator is
 * used
 * to comprehensively assess the population
 * . This implementation can be useful
 * when generating convergence plots.
 *
 * @return new data
 */
@Override
public double [][] createData()
{
    double performance = _indicator.evaluate(
        _ea);
    return new double [][]{{_ea.
        getCurrentGeneration(), performance}};
}

```

Listing 35: IPerformanceIndicator interface

```

/**
 * Interfaces for classes responsible for
 * evaluating the performance of EA's.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface IPerformanceIndicator
{
    /**
     * Main method for evaluating EA's
     * performance
     *
     * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
     * @return performance value
     */
    double evaluate(EA ea);
}

```

3. Example implementation for solving a knapsack problem [T]

This section showcases how the evolutionary module can solve an optimization problem. As a didactic example, a well-known knapsack problem will be used as a test problem. The problem instance used will be small and highly synthetical for convenience (the section is focused on using the evolutionary computation module, not particularly on conducting state-of-the-art optimizations). In the following sections, the precise definition of the tackled problem will be presented, the implementations

of evolutionary methods will be introduced, and small experiments will be conducted to exhibit the usability of these algorithms.

3.1. Problem definition

A standard knapsack problem can be defined as follows:

$$\max \sum_{i=1}^n v_i x_i, \quad (1)$$

$$s.t. \sum_{i=1}^n s_i x_i \leq t, \quad (2)$$

$$\forall_{i=1, \dots, n} x_i \in \{0, 1\}, v_i, s_i \in \mathcal{R}_{\geq 0}. \quad (3)$$

where n denotes the number of available items that can be put into a knapsack, v_i and s_i , denote the value and size of an i -th item, \mathbf{x} is a binary decision vector whose i -th element dictates whether an item should be put into the knapsack or not, and t is the knapsack capacity. The goal is to find a subset of items that can be put into the knapsack without violating its capacity and maximize their total value.

The following tutorials assume that $n = 30$, and the items' values and sizes are listed in Table 1. It is a seasonably small problem instance that will allow mainly focusing on the implementation part, not the optimization challenges per se. It is assumed that $t = 50$ if not stated otherwise. For such a setting, the optimal solution comprises items marked with asterisks in Table 1, yielding a total value and size of 93 and 50.

3.2. Solution approach

We will use a straightforward approach to solve the knapsack problem. Specifically, a standard generational, population-based evolutionary method that aligns with the pseudocode listed in Algorithm 1 will be implemented. That is, the method will maintain a population of specimens, and, in each generation, it will generate an entirely new population of offspring solutions by reproducing the parents selected from the current population. The offspring will be evaluated and merged with the current population. Then, the combined population will be sorted according to performance, and the worst part of it will be removed, passing thus the best solutions found so far to the next generation. Note that this scheme well-aligns with the phases' default implementations illustrated in Figure 3. Consequently, a few of them are required to be adapted to create a final solution approach.

Regarding solution representation and evaluation, direct encoding will be employed. Each specimen will be modeled as a n -element boolean decision vector when n denotes the number of items. During the evaluation phase, each specimen will be assigned a two-element performance vector consisting of the total value and size yielded by used items. Additionally, the performance will be stored as the auxiliary value (associated with the wrapped alternative). It will be employed, e.g., by the sorting procedure or the tournament selection (to identify the tournament winner).

Item	Value	Size
1*	10	5
2	6	4
3	3	2
4*	7	4
5	5	8
6*	8	5
7	2	3
8*	5	1
9	7	9
10*	3	2
11	5	8
12*	12	4
13*	5	3
14	8	8
15	4	7
16	2	7
17*	8	5
18	7	6
19*	15	10
20*	12	8
21	10	9
22	7	7
23	3	4
24	1	4
25	5	4
26*	5	1
27*	3	2
28	15	14
29	5	5
30	1	1

Table 1: Data used for the knapsack problem (items that form an optimal solutions for $t = 50$ are marked with asterisks)

Note that the specimen may become infeasible after evaluation, given the assumed knapsack capacity. This tutorial considers two basic means of dealing with infeasibility (exclusive): applying a penalty and restoring the feasibility using a repair procedure. The latter is usually a better option in terms of efficiency (but also often more challenging to implement). Both modes will operate during the evaluation phase (e.g., a solution will be immediately repaired after the evaluation).

The penalty approach will be modeled by suitably implementing the fitness score assigned to the solution (auxiliary score). Specifically, the following formula will be used (the more, the better):

$$specimen\ fitness = \begin{cases} total\ value, & \text{if } total\ size \leq t \\ t - total\ size, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This way, the final solution ranking will prioritize the feasible solutions (the higher the value, the better). Then. The ranking will be filled with infeasible ones in decreasing order of the degree to which they exceed the allowed capacity.

In the latter option, any infeasible solution will be repaired by removing items from the knapsack until feasibility is restored. The items will be removed in increasing order of their value/size ratio to prioritize the removal of low-value items that take up a lot of space.

Regarding the specimen selection step, a tournament selection of size two will be employed. It is also assumed that a pair of solutions will be designated to construct a single offspring.

When it comes to the reproduction step, a standard single-point crossover operator will be used to construct an offspring decision vector from two selected parents. Next, a simple flip mutation will be employed: each binary value in the offspring vector will have a chance to flip with the probability of $1/n$.

3.3. Designed algorithm

This section illustrates how to implement an evolutionary algorithm delineated in Section 3.2. Note that the algorithm implements the default algorithmic scheme presented in Algorithm 1 and vastly uses the default phases' implementation summarized in Figure 3. Therefore, only a few adaptations are required to build one's own method. The following sections are devoted to them. All the sources can be found in `t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t1_knapsack_problem` package.

3.3.1. Data container

Source: `t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t1_knapsack_problem.common.Data`

First, the framework does not provide any means for problem data modeling. Thus, it is recommended to implement a container-like class that will store the problem-related data. Such a container can then be redistributed among the algorithm's interrelated algorithm components, providing convenient data access. For this tutorial, a `Data` class was implemented (see Listing 36). It is a straightforward, self-explanatory class that handles the problem instance data.

Listing 36: Data class

```

public class Data
{
    /**
     * Knapsack capacity.
     */
    public final int _capacity;

    /**
     * Knapsack capacity.
     *
     * @param capacity knapsack capacity.
     */
    public Data(int capacity)
    {
        _capacity = capacity;
    }

    /**

```

Listing 37: KnapsackConstructor class

```

20  * The number of items.
    */
    public int _items = 30;

    /**
25  * Values (i-th index = i-th item).
    */
    public final double[] _values = new
        double[]{
    10.0d, 6.0d, 3.0d, 7.0d, 5.0d, 8.0d, 2.0d
        , 5.0d, 7.0d, 3.0d, 5.0d, 12.0d, 5.0d,
        8.0d, 4.0d, 2.0d, 8.0d, 7.0d, 15.0d,
        12.0d, 10.0d, 7.0d, 3.0d, 1.0d, 5.0d,
        5.0d, 3.0d, 15.0d, 5.0d, 1.0d};

    /**
30  * Sizes (i-th index = i-th item).
    */
    public final int[] _sizes = new int[]{5,
        4, 2, 4, 8, 5, 3, 1, 9, 2, 8, 4, 3, 8,
        7, 7, 5, 6, 10, 8, 9, 7, 4, 4, 4, 1,
        2, 14, 5, 1,};

    /**
35  * Item indices sorted according to value
        [item]/size[item] ratio.
    */
    public final int[] _sortedIndices = new
        int[]{23, 15, 14, 4, 10, 6, 22, 8, 13,
        21, 28, 29, 27, 20, 17, 24, 1, 2, 9,
        18, 19, 26, 5, 16, 12, 3, 0, 11, 7,
        25};
}

```

```

public class KnapsackConstructor implements
    IConstruct
{
    /**
5   * Data container.
    */
    private final Data _data;

    /**
10  * Parameterized constructor.
    *
    * @param data data container.
    */
    public KnapsackConstructor(Data data)
    {
15        _data = data;
    }

    /**
20  * Creates initial population (array of
        specimens) of size "population size
        ".
    * The population consists of random
        solutions to the knapsack problem.
    *
    * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
    * @return specimen array
    * @throws PhaseException the exception
        can be thrown and propagated higher
    */
    @Override
    public ArrayList<Specimen>
        createInitialPopulation(EA ea) throws
        PhaseException
    {
30        int ps = ea.getPopulationSize(); //
            number of specimens = population
            size
        ArrayList<Specimen> specimens = new
            ArrayList<>(ps); // instantiate the
            array
        for (int i = 0; i < ps; i++) // iterate
            the required number of times
        {
            boolean[] itemUsed = new boolean[
                _data._items]; // create random
                boolean vector (item used or not)
            for (int j = 0; j < _data._items; j
                ++) itemUsed[j] = ea.getRNG().
                nextBoolean();
            Specimen s = new Specimen(2); //
                create specimen; 2 = the number of
                criteria (value; size)
            Chromosome c = new Chromosome(
                itemUsed); // create the
                chromosome (decision space;
                boolean vector is passed)
            s.setChromosome(c); // set specimen's
                chromosome
            specimens.add(s); // store the

```

3.3.2. Constructor

Source: *t1.t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t1_knapsack_problem.common.KnapsackConstructor*

Let's now move to constructing an initial population. This implementation will use the default processing imposed by the *Phases.ConstructInitialPopulation* class (delegates the specimen construction to *IConstruct* object; creates the specimen container; turns on the "evaluation" and "ID assignment" flags). Therefore, only a dedicated implementation of the *IConstruct* implementation is required.

The proposed implementation is brought in Listing 37 for convenience (*KnapsackConstructor*). Noticeably, it is given access to the data container when created. The main method (*createInitialPopulation*) creates a specimen array of an *ea.getPopulationSize*. Each specimen is constructed in a loop, where one iteration begins with constructing a boolean random decision vector of a size that equals the number of items. Next, a new (empty) specimen object is created. It is immediately supplied with a chromosome that wraps the drawn decision vector (such a chromosome is instantiated with one gene that handles the decision vector). Finally, the iteration ends by adding the initial random specimen to the specimen array, which the implemented method returns.

```

        specimen
    }
    return specimens;
}
}

```

3.3.3. Reproducer

Source: *t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t1_knapsack_problem.common.KnapsackReproducer*

This section delineates how the reproduction step was implemented. The implementation makes use of the delegation to the *IReproduce* object (the default *Reproduce* class is employed as the *AbstractReproducePhase* object).

The implementation of the *IReproduce* interface is given in Listing 38. During the initialization, the object instance being constructed creates two reproduction operators: *reproduction.operators.crossover.SinglePointCrossover* and *reproduction.operators.mutation.Flip* (the reader is recommended to examine these classes on their own).

The main method (“*createOffspring*”) creates a new specimen array of size “*ea.getOffspringSize*” using parent specimens stored in “*ea.getSpecimenContainer().getParents()*”. It is assumed that each “*Parents*” object will consist of two accessible parent specimens.

The offspring creation is done in the main loop, where each iteration starts with retrieving boolean decision vectors of selected parents. Next, the crossover operator is applied to them to construct the offspring decision vector, followed by the mutation operator that introduces minor perturbations. Finally, the new specimen (offspring) is formed from the resulting vector and added to the offspring array, which the method returns in the end.

Listing 38: KnapsackReproducer class

```

public class KnapsackReproducer implements
    IReproduce
{
    /**
     * Single point crossover operator.
     */
    private final SinglePointCrossover _SPC;

    /**
     * Flip mutation operator.
     */
    private final Flip _FM;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param data data container.
     * @param R random number generator;
     */
    public KnapsackReproducer(Data data,
        IRandom R)
    {

```

```

        // instantiate the crossover and
        // mutation operators
        _SPC = new SinglePointCrossover();
        _FM = new Flip(new Flip.Params(1.0d / (
            double) data._items));
    }

    /**
     * Creates an array of offspring
     * specimens (of size equal to ‘‘
     * offspring size’’).
     *
     * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
     * @return offspring specimens
     */
    @Override
    public ArrayList<Specimen>
        createOffspring(EA ea)
    {
        int os = ea.getOffspringSize(); // get
            the offspring size
        ArrayList<Specimen> offspring = new
            ArrayList<>(os);

        for (int i = 0; i < os; i++)
        {
            // it is assumed that no. parents =
            // offspring size; and there will be
            // 2 parents per one offspring
            Parents parents = ea.
                getSpecimenContainer().getParents
                    ().get(i);
            Specimen p1 = parents._parents.get(0)
                ;
            Specimen p2 = parents._parents.get(1)
                ;
            boolean[] bv1 = p1.
                getBooleanDecisionVector();
            boolean[] bv2 = p2.
                getBooleanDecisionVector();

            // do crossover
            boolean[] ob = _SPC.crossover(bv1,
                bv2, ea.getR()); // apply single
                point crossover and create
                offspring decision vector

            // do mutation
            _FM.mutate(ob, ea.getR());

            // create the specimen
            Chromosome chromosome = new
                Chromosome(ob);
            Specimen specimen = new Specimen(2);
            specimen.setChromosome(chromosome);
            offspring.add(specimen);
        }

        return offspring;
    }
}

```

3.3.4. Evaluator

Source: `t1.t10.t2.evolutionary.computation.module.t1.knapsack.problem.common.KnapsackEvaluator`

As with the construction and reproduction steps, the evaluation uses the default phase's implementation (*Evaluate*), but it implements the dedicated interface to which the processing is delegated: *IEvaluate*.

The implementation is in Listing 39 (*KnapsackEvaluate*). First, a data container and a flag that determines if a repairing procedure should be utilized (if not, a penalty is applied) are passed via the constructor.

The main method (*evaluateSpecimens*) comprises a main loop that iterates over the input specimens. Each specimen is evaluated as imposed by its boolean decision vector, i.e., a *i*-th element is considered put in the knapsack if the *i*-th flag is set to true. Both the total value and size are calculated in this step.

If the "repair mode" is on and the total size exceeds the knapsack capacity, the method triggers the removal of the least promising items. This process iterates over "sorted indices" (shows an order of elements – pointed by indices – in which value/size ratio monotonically increases). Naturally, an object can be removed from the knapsack only if it is already in it. If it is not, the "repairing loop" continues. When removing an item, the total value and size are suitably adjusted. If the updated size satisfies the knapsack capacity, the repairing loop terminates (although the process could start inserting the most efficient items if there is some space left).

After the conditional execution of the repairing procedure is completed, the total value and size of the specimen being evaluated are stored as a two-element performance vector. Furthermore, the total value is stored as an auxiliary value (used as a sorting criterion).

Finally, evaluating a single specimen ends with the conditional application of a penalty (when repairing was not used and the size exceeded the capacity). The calculated penalty is used as an updated specimen's auxiliary value.

Listing 39: KnapsackEvaluator class

```
public class KnapsackEvaluator implements
    IEvaluate
{
    /**
     * Data container.
     */
    private final Data _data;

    /**
     * If true, infeasible solutions will be
     * immediately repaired by removing
     * items from the knapsack in the
     * increasing
     * order of their value/size ratios until
     * the feasibility is restored. If
     * false, the algorithm works in "
     * penalty mode".
     */
}
```

```
public final boolean _repairMode;

/**
 * Parameterized constructor.
 *
 * @param data data container
 * @param repairMode if true, infeasible
 * solutions will be immediately
 * repaired by removing items from the
 * knapsack
 * in the increasing order of their
 * value/size ratios until the
 * feasibility is restored;
 * if false, the algorithm works in "
 * penalty mode"
 */
public KnapsackEvaluator(Data data,
    boolean repairMode)
{
    _data = data;
    _repairMode = repairMode;
}

/**
 * Evaluates specimens.
 *
 * @param specimens array of specimens to
 * be evaluated
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public void evaluateSpecimens(ArrayList<
    Specimen> specimens) throws
    PhaseException
{
    for (Specimen s : specimens)
    {
        boolean[] used = s.
            getBooleanDecisionVector(); // get
            the decision vector

        double value = 0.0d;
        int size = 0;
        for (int i = 0; i < _data._items; i++)
            // update knapsack total size and
            value
            if (used[i])
            {
                value += _data._values[i];
                size += _data._sizes[i];
            }

        if ((_repairMode) && (size > _data.
            _capacity)) // if the repair mode is
            used
        {
            for (int index : _data._sortedIndices
                )
            {
                if (!used[index]) continue; // if
                item is used, it cannot be
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```

55     removed
used[index] = false; // remove the
    item
size -= _data._sizes[index]; //
    update the value
value -= _data._values[index]; //
    update the size
if (size <= _data._capacity) break;
    // break if the feasibility is
    restored
}

60 // Extra: some extra space may be
    left; one may try adding items
    that fit (starting from the ones
// that have the best value/size
    ratio.

// not really needed, the ‘‘
    getBooleanDecisionVector’’ method
    returns a reference (not copy)
65 //s.setBooleanDecisionVector(used);
}

s.setEvaluations(new double []{value,
    size}); // set the performance
    vector
s.setAuxScore(value);

70 if ((!_repairMode) && (size > _data.
    _capacity))// if the penalty mode is
    used
s.setAuxScore(_data._capacity - size);
}
}
75 }

```

What is more, the “*instantiateDefaultValues*” method is overwritten to instantiate, by default, the developed *IConstruct* (*KnapsackConstructor*), *IReproduce* (*KnapsackReproducer*), and *IEvaluate* (*KnapsackEvaluator*) implementations (they could also be created in the constructor). Typically, these are intended to be provided by the user explicitly via the params container, as they are more problem-related than algorithm-related components. Nonetheless, this tutorial implementation shows how to use such a shortcut for convenience (the method is called by the parent class constructor at the beginning).

Additionally, it is recommended to think about more generalized implementation paths (some elements are hard-coded intentionally). For instance, the custom reproduction (or their parameters) could be passed via the params constructor. The only adjustable parameter is now the knapsack capacity (provided via the params container).

Finally, this class extension adjusts the sorting phase. The default implementation in the *ea.AbstractEABundle* class creates the sorting phase that ranks the solutions according to their auxiliary value in ascending order. However, the way the auxiliary score was defined in *KnapsackEvaluator* recommends greater values. It conflicts with the default implementation of the remove phase that preserves the first half of the combined population (not the last). Therefore, this bundle overwrites the default initialization of the sorting phase so that the specimens are ordered in descending order of auxiliary values (“false” flag). Alternatively, one could redefine the auxiliary score in *KnapsackEvaluator*, leaving the sorting step unchanged. Nonetheless, remembering that the selection procedure used (parent selection) may exploit the auxiliary scores is worth remembering. If so, properly adjusting their preference direction can again be of great concern.

Listing 40: KnapsackEABundle class

```

public class KnapsackEABundle extends
    AbstractEABundle
{
    public static class Params extends
        AbstractEABundle.Params
    {
5         /**
        * Data container.
        */
        public final Data _data;

10        /**
        * If true, infeasible solutions will
        be immediately repaired by removing
        items from the knapsack in the
        increasing
        * order of their value/size ratios
        until the feasibility is restored.
        If false, the algorithm works in "
        penalty mode".
        */
        public final boolean _repairMode;

15        /**

```

3.3.5. Algorithm bundle

Source: *t1.t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t1_knapsack_problem.common.KnapsackEABundle*

At this stage, all the components that differ from the default implementations are developed. One can now instantiate all the phases and wrap them using the *ea.EA* class, but it would be fatiguing from a long-term perspective. The better idea is to extend the *AbstractEABundle* class to create a customized composition of phases and formulate dedicated parameterization means.

The custom bundle (*KnapsackEABundle*) created for this tutorial is shown in Listing 40. As mentioned, the algorithm primarily uses the phases instantiated by default by the *AbstractEABundle* class (see Section 2.10.2). This means that not many adjustments are needed, making the process of creating a custom bundle straightforward and manageable.

First, the custom bundle can accept three dedicated fields via the extended params container (via its constructor; the access is protected): the data container (capacity) and the flag indicating whether the repair mode is used or not.

```

20 * Parameterized constructor.
21 *
22 * @param capacity knapsack capacity
23 * @param repairMode if true,
24   infeasible solutions will be
25   immediately repaired by removing
26   items from the knapsack
27 *
28   in the increasing
29   order of their value/size ratios
30   until the feasibility is restored;
31 *
32   if false, the
33   algorithm works in "penalty mode"
34 */
35 public Params(int capacity, boolean
36   repairMode)
37 {
38   super("EA (repair = " + repairMode +
39     ")", Criteria.constructCriteria(
40     new String[]{"Value", "Size"}, new
41     boolean[]{true, false});
42   _data = new Data(capacity);
43   _repairMode = repairMode;
44 }
45
46 /**
47  * Auxiliary method called by the
48  * constructor at the beginning to
49  * instantiate default params values (
50  * optional).
51  * This implementation instantiates
52  * phases-related objects.
53  */
54 @Override
55 protected void instantiateDefaultValues
56   ()
57 {
58   if (_construct == null) _construct =
59     new KnapsackConstructor(_data);
60   if (_evaluate == null) _evaluate =
61     new KnapsackEvaluator(_data,
62     _repairMode);
63   if (_reproduce == null) _reproduce =
64     new KnapsackReproducer(_data, _R);
65 }
66
67 /**
68  * The method is overwritten to
69  * instantiate the {@link phase.
70  * SortByAuxValue} phase.
71  *
72  * @param p params container
73  */
74 @Override
75 protected void instantiateSortPhase(
76   AbstractEABundle.Params p)
77 {
78   _phasesBundle._sort = new
79     SortByAuxValue(false);
80 }
81
82 [...]

```

```

}

```

3.3.6. Instantiating the evolutionary algorithm

Source: *t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t1_knapsack_problem.common.Utils*

Finally, it is worth facilitating the creation of an instance of an evolutionary algorithm (*ea.EA*). Note that the evolutionary algorithm comprises parameters specific to higher-level processing than those linked to the *AbstractEABundle* class (e.g., a population size). Therefore, introducing additional wrapping may be convenient. For this reason, one can create a method that will employ the developed *KnapsackEABundle* and use it to tune the evolutionary algorithm. A straightforward implementation of such a wrapping is provided in the *Utils.getKnapsackEA* method, whose self-explanatory code is brought in Listing 41 for convenience (note that the code involves supplying the bundle with the tournament selection).

Listing 41: *Utils.getKnapsackEA* method

```

5 /**
6  * Auxiliary method that creates an
7  * evolutionary algorithm for solving the
8  * knapsack problem.
9  *
10 * @param populationSize population size
11   (equals the offspring size)
12 * @param R random number generator
13 * @param knapsackCapacity knapsack
14   capacity
15 * @param repairMode if true, infeasible
16   solutions will be immediately repaired
17   by removing items from the knapsack
18 * in the increasing order of their value/
19   size ratios until the feasibility is
20   restored;
21 * if false, the algorithm works in "
22   penalty mode"
23 * @return instance of {@link EA}.
24 */
25 public static EA getKnapsackEA(int
26   populationSize, IRandom R, int
27   knapsackCapacity, boolean repairMode)
28 {
29   // Create the bundle params container:
30   KnapsackEABundle.Params pB = new
31     KnapsackEABundle.Params(
32     knapsackCapacity, repairMode);
33
34   // Use a tournament selection (the winner
35   is selected based on the aux value;
36   greater values are preferred)
37   Tournament.Params pTournament = new
38     Tournament.Params(2, populationSize);
39   pTournament._preferenceDirection = true;
40   // greater values are preferred
41   pB._select = new Tournament(pTournament);
42   // offspring size

```

```

// Create the parameterized bundle:
KnapsackEABundle bundle = new
    KnapsackEABundle(pB);

// Create the EA params container:
EA.Params pEA = new EA.Params(bundle.
    _name, pB._criteria);
// Transfer all phases from the bundle to
EA:
PhasesBundle.copyPhasesFromBundleToEA(pEA
    , bundle._phasesBundle);
// Set EA id:
pEA._id = 0;
// Set the random number generator (
    accessible from the ea object)"
pEA._R = R;
// Set the population size (and offspring
    size):
pEA._populationSize = populationSize;
pEA._offspringSize = populationSize; // (
    equals the population size size)
return new EA(pEA);
}

```

3.4. Example experiments

This section introduces some basic example experiments that showcase how the evolutionary algorithm finally established in Section 3.4 can be employed to solve the knapsack problem.

3.4.1. Creating and running the algorithm

Source package:
t1.t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.
t1_knapsack_problem.t1

This introductory tutorial shows how to create and manually execute an instance of the evolutionary method (i.e., without using the *IRunner* object). Since the method's parameterization is mostly done in *Utils.getKnapsackEA*, the amount of code in this tutorial is reduced to a bare minimum. It is brought in Listing 42.

First, the code instantiates the random number generator and introduces some basic parameters, e.g., the population size. Next, it creates the instance of the evolutionary algorithm. Finally, the *init* and *step* methods of *ea.EA* are manually executed (*init* just once, *step* a *generations - 1* number of times). Note that they can throw an exception. Therefore, they are put in the try-catch blocks (the exceptions are not explicitly handled). Note that the code prints a summary of a selected number of the best-performing specimens in each iteration. The console output that is focused on the first generations is depicted in Figure 5.

Listing 42: Creating and running the algorithm

```

// Set basic variables:
IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(0);
int populationSize = 10;

```

```

int knapsackCapacity = 50;
int generations = 20;
boolean repair = true;

// Retrieve the parameterized instance of
the EA
EA knapsackEA = Utils.getKnapsackEA(
    populationSize, R, knapsackCapacity,
    repair);

// Sets the upper limit for the specimens
to be printed per each generation
int printLimit = 5;

try
{
    System.out.println("Initialization (
        generation = 0):");
    // Call the init method:
    knapsackEA.init();

    // Print specimen data:
    //noinspection DataFlowIssue
    for (int i = 0; i < Math.min(printLimit,
        populationSize); i++)
    {
        Specimen s = knapsackEA.
            getSpecimensContainer().
            getPopulation().get(i);
        Utils.printSpecimenData(s, true);
    }
} catch (EAException e)
{
    throw new RuntimeException(e);
}

// Perform a desired number of generations:
for (int g = 1; g < generations; g++)
{
    System.out.println("Generation = " + g +
        ":");
    try
    {
        // Execute the step method:
        knapsackEA.step(new EATimestamp(g, 0));

        // Print specimen data:
        //noinspection DataFlowIssue
        for (int i = 0; i < Math.min(printLimit
            , populationSize); i++)
        {
            Specimen s = knapsackEA.
                getSpecimensContainer().
                getPopulation().get(i);
            Utils.printSpecimenData(s, true);
        }
    } catch (EAException e)
    {
        throw new RuntimeException(e);
    }
}

```

```
}  
}
```

3.4.2. Using the Runner object

```
Source package:  
t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.  
t1 knapsack_problem.t2
```

The following tutorial employs the *Runner* object to take control of executing the *init* and *step* methods instead of calling them manually. The changes in the code are minor (a few lines of code) and straightforward. Hence, they are not brought here for the sake of clarity. Nonetheless, the expected outcome of running the source code is the same as the one presented in Figure 5.

3.4.3. Reporting the performance using a scatter plot

```
Source package:  
t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.  
t1 knapsack_problem.t3
```

This tutorial shows how a visualization module can be coupled with the evolutionary algorithm to illustrate the method's performance over time. Specifically, the case in this tutorial is to generate a scatter plot depicting populations generated by the algorithm throughout generations. The X and Y dimensions are assumed to represent the total value and size yielded by the generated knapsacks. Furthermore, each population will be illustrated using a different color, selected from the gradient and based on the generation number. This way, the overall method's progression can be observed. Additionally, a horizontal line will be illustrated on the plot to mark the knapsack capacity threshold.

Note that the source code of this tutorial begins with creating a *Plot2D* object with a suitably parameterized display ranges manager (en extra, i.e., the third display range is constructed and is assumed to be linked with the generation number). However, the visualization module was already introduced in the previous tutorial series. Hence, this code snippet is not presented here for convenience. Instead, the provided Listing 43 focuses on the parameterization of the *Runner* object.

Instantiating the *IVisualization* object (to be coupled with the runner) is mostly about parameterizing the data updater. In this tutorial, the populations generated by the evolutionary algorithm and the horizontal line (capacity threshold) are intended to be displayed. Therefore, the data updater is supplied with two sources (population- and line-related), each connected to a dedicated data processor. Finally, the processors are mapped to the same *Plot2D*.

The code begins by constructing population-related objects. First, an *EASource* is created using the evolutionary algorithm instance. It aggregates all the specimens' performance vectors into a matrix by default. However, the source is parameterized to extend these vectors by the current generation and steady-state repeat numbers (the third and fourth attributes). Next,

a dedicated processor is constructed. It uses the "cumulative" mode (the input flag is set to true), meaning that the final data will be composed of the current and the past data (if the input flag is false, only the current population would be rendered). Finally, a reference data set is constructed (marker points drawn as circles and colored using a gradient based on the third display range – mapped with the third attribute, i.e., generation number).

Listing 43: Reporting the performance using a scatter plot

```
[...]  
// Create the EA-related source, processor,  
// and reference data set (style):  
IDataSource sourceEA = new EASource(  
    knapsackEA, true);  
IDataProcessor dataProcessorEA = new  
    DataProcessor(true);  
5 MarkerStyle ms = new MarkerStyle(2.0f,  
    Gradient.getViridisGradient(), 2, Marker  
    .CIRCLE);  
IDataSet referenceEA = DataSet.getFor2D(  
    knapsackEA.getName(), ms);  
  
// Create the dummy data source (line  
// defined by two points):  
IDataSource sourceLine = new  
    CyclicDataSource(new double [][]{{0.0d,  
    knapsackCapacity}, {150.0d,  
    knapsackCapacity}});  
10 IDataProcessor dataProcessorLine = new  
    DataProcessor();  
IDataSet referenceLine = DataSet.getFor2D("  
    Capacity", new LineStyle(0.25f, Color.  
    BLACK));  
  
// Create data updater:  
DataUpdater dataUpdater;  
15 try  
    {  
        DataUpdater.Params pDU = new DataUpdater.  
            Params(frame.getModel().  
                getPlotsWrapper());  
        // Two sources:  
20 pDU._dataSources = new IDataSource []{  
            sourceEA, sourceLine};  
        // Two processors  
        pDU._dataProcessors = new IDataProcessor  
            []{dataProcessorEA, dataProcessorLine  
            };  
        // Sources->Processors are linked 1:1  
        pDU._sourcesToProcessors = new  
            SourceToProcessors []{  
25 new SourceToProcessors(0),  
            new SourceToProcessors(1)  
        };  
        // Both processors point to the same plot  
        // (each uses a dedicated reference data  
        // set style):  
        pDU._processorToPlots = new  
            ProcessorToPlots []
```

```

Initialization (generation = 0):
Specimen = 0 0 0 9: [value = 76.0; size = 45.0; aux = 76.0] 010101010101100010011000000000
Specimen = 0 0 0 8: [value = 76.0; size = 48.0; aux = 76.0] 101100000101000011010000101011
Specimen = 0 0 0 4: [value = 76.0; size = 47.0; aux = 76.0] 111100000001110011000000010010
Specimen = 0 0 0 0: [value = 75.0; size = 45.0; aux = 75.0] 100101010100000010101000011001
Specimen = 0 0 0 6: [value = 70.0; size = 46.0; aux = 70.0] 000000010001100011001100110011
Generation = 1:
Specimen = 0 1 0 2: [value = 76.0; size = 47.0; aux = 76.0] 111100000001110011000000010010
Specimen = 0 1 0 1: [value = 76.0; size = 48.0; aux = 76.0] 101100000101000011010000101011
Specimen = 0 1 0 0: [value = 76.0; size = 45.0; aux = 76.0] 010101010101100010011000000000
Specimen = 0 1 0 3: [value = 75.0; size = 45.0; aux = 75.0] 100101010100000010101000011001
Specimen = 0 1 0 4: [value = 70.0; size = 46.0; aux = 70.0] 000000010001100011001100110011
Generation = 2:
Specimen = 0 2 0 6: [value = 79.0; size = 48.0; aux = 79.0] 111100000001100011010000101001
Specimen = 0 2 0 2: [value = 78.0; size = 50.0; aux = 78.0] 010100010101100011010100000011
Specimen = 0 1 0 0: [value = 76.0; size = 45.0; aux = 76.0] 010101010101100010011000000000
Specimen = 0 1 0 1: [value = 76.0; size = 48.0; aux = 76.0] 101100000101000011010000101011
Specimen = 0 1 0 2: [value = 76.0; size = 47.0; aux = 76.0] 111100000001110011000000010010
Generation = 3:
Specimen = 0 3 0 0: [value = 80.0; size = 49.0; aux = 80.0] 100101010100000010101000111001
Specimen = 0 3 0 1: [value = 79.0; size = 48.0; aux = 79.0] 111100000001100011010000101001

```

Figure 5: Expected console output

```

30 {
    new ProcessorToPlots(0, referenceEA),
    new ProcessorToPlots(0, referenceLine)
};
    dataUpdater = new DataUpdater(pDU);
35 } catch (Exception e)
{
    throw new RuntimeException(e);
}
40 // Create the visualization object
IVisualization visualization = new
    Visualization(frame, dataUpdater);

Runner.Params pR = new Runner.Params(
    knapsackEA);
    // Set the visualization mode:
45 pR._visualization = visualization;
pR._displayMode = DisplayMode.
    FROM_THE_BEGINNING;
pR._updaterMode = UpdaterMode.
    AFTER_GENERATION;
IRunner runner = new Runner(pR);
50 [...]
```

The code next creates the line-related objects. First, a “CyclicDataSource” is used. It supplies the updater with one

of the pre-defined (fixed) data sets. The current data set to be returned is cyclical (the index pointing to current data is incremented after each call and returns to 0 when the limit is exceeded). Providing only one data set will effectively result in a constant output produced by this source. Hence, the code specifies the coordinates of two extreme points that define the horizontal line as such a data set. This way, it will be constantly used when updating the rendering data. The processor used is a default processor that does not use the cumulative mode. At the same time, the reference data set is parameterized so that the two fixed data points will be illustrated as a horizontal line with a black color.

Next, the instance of the data updater is created in the try-catch block. The code sets the sources and processors and establishes the desired data flow (mappings). The created object instance is forwarded to the *Visualization* object being created. Note that the latter also has to be supplied with the frame object. The visualization object is then used to parameterize the runner. Note that the “_displayMode” and “_updaterMode” flags are specified. Specifically, the data updater is set to be executed after each generation of the evolutionary algorithm. At the same time, the frame will be made visible by the runner prior to the execution of the algorithm.

The expected final outcomes of this tutorial are illustrated in Figures 6 and 7. The first exhibits the performance of the implemented method when the repairing mode is turned on, while the

Figure 6: The final scatter plot (the algorithm employs a repairing procedure)

Figure 7: The final scatter plot (the algorithm does not employ a repairing procedure)

latter concerns the penalization of infeasible specimens. Note that the scales for the gradient are the same, meaning that the progression of both method variants is comparable. It is evident that the performance of the “repairing” method is much better as it much sooner discovers the optimum (this is the true optimum shown in Section 3.1). Noticeably, the latter algorithm can maintain infeasible solutions (i.e., it is not guaranteed that the population will only consist of the feasible ones). Indeed, the scatter plots reported some solutions in the infeasible area

(above the horizontal line – the capacity threshold).

3.4.4. Combining results of different runs

Source package:
`t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.`
`t1 knapsack_problem.t4`

The following tutorial highlights that the classic knapsack problem can be viewed as a two-objective optimization problem (there is a conflict between minimizing the total size and maximizing the total value). However, no multi-objective algorithm was used to solve a knapsack problem viewed in this way. Instead, the source code instantiates multiple instances of an evolutionary algorithm, each with a different knapsack capacity limit set. They are intended to be run simultaneously (by the Runner object), and their final populations will be used as input data sets for rendering. Also, each population will be illustrated using different color markers (black-red gradient based on the capacity limit). Since the source code is a straight reformulation of the one introduced in the previous section, it is not presented here (it is recommended to check how the whole evolution was executed by calling the “executeEvolution” method of the runner object). The final render is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The final scatter plot that illustrates joint results.

3.4.5. Reporting the performance using a convergence plot

Source package:
`t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.`
`t1 knapsack_problem.t5`

This tutorial presents how a convergence plot can be used along with the evolutionary algorithm to report the latter’s perfor-

mance over time. The case is to illustrate how the minimal, average, and maximal knapsack values yielded by the population members were changing throughout subsequent generations of the evolutionary run. The code snippet in Listing 44 focuses on establishing a data updater (the rest of the source code does not present anything new).

First, the “*GenerationAndStatistics*” source is used. This implementation constructs an output array that consists of a generation number and – specified by the user – statistics on a selected performance value of each specimen in the population (the index pointing to the element of a performance array can be specified). This form aligns with the required form of a data set imposed by the convergence plot: $[X, Y, Y - deviation, Y + deviation]$. Therefore, the *Min()*, *Mean()*, and *Max()* (implement *IStatistic*) were used in the data source (and the index pointing to specimens’ performance arrays was set to 0 – total value stored). Next, a default processor with the cumulative mode turned on was used to aggregate the statistics attained throughout all generations. Finally, a reference data set with a specified envelope color was instantiated. All these three objects were used to establish a data updater with the most straightforward data flow (source → processor → plot).

Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the statistics on the total value throughout all generations attained by the evolutionary method with the “repair” and “penalty” modes used. Clearly, the former algorithm proved more efficient.

Listing 44: Reporting the performance using a convergence plot

```
[...]
// Create the EA-related source, processor,
// and reference data set (style):
// The source produces a single data point
// from the current population: [generation
// , mean value, min value, and max value],
// which is compatible with the input data
// for the convergence plot.
IDataSource source = new
    GenerationAndStatistics(knapsackEA, new
        IStatistic[]{new Mean(), new Max(), new
            Min()}, 0);
// Cumulative = true to capture all points
// generated throughout all generations.
IDataProcessor dataProcessor = new
    DataProcessor(true);

IDataSet referenceDS = DataSet.
    getForConvergencePlot2D(knapsackEA.
        getName(), new LineStyle(0.5f, new
            Color(0.0f, 0.8f, 0.0f)), new color.
            Color(0.0f, 1.0f, 0.0f, 0.2f));
//IDataSet referenceDS = DataSet.
//    getForConvergencePlot2D(knapsackEA.
//        getName(), new LineStyle(0.5f, new
//            Color(0.8f, 0.0f, 0.0f)), new color.
//                Color(1.0f, 0.0f, 0.0f, 0.2f));
// Create data updater:
DataUpdater dataUpdater;
try
```

```
{
    dataUpdater = DataUpdater.
        getSimpleDataUpdater(frame.getModel
            ().getPlotsWrapper(), source,
            dataProcessor, referenceDS);
} catch (Exception e)
{
    throw new RuntimeException(e);
}
[...]
```


Figure 9: The final convergence plot (the algorithm employs a repairing procedure)

3.4.6. Reporting the performance using a multi-plot visualization window

Source package:
t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.
t1 knapsack_problem.t6

The final experimentation section uses the implementations introduced in the previous ones. Specifically, it shows how a multi-plot visualization window can be coupled with the execution of evolutionary algorithms. It is assumed that the visualization window consists of three plots:

1. A scatter plot that reveals the method’s comprehensive performance when the “repair” mode is used.
2. A scatter plot that reveals the method’s comprehensive performance when the “penalty” mode is used.
3. A convergence plot that illustrates the min/average/max values yielded by solutions generated throughout all generations by the two algorithms mentioned above.

Figure 10: The final convergence plot (the algorithm does not employ a repairing procedure)

The source code is a straightforward reformulation of the previous ones. Hence, it is not brought here to avoid redundancy. However, the final render generated by this tutorial’s code is illustrated in Figure 11.

4. Example implementation for maximizing a continuous function of two variables [T]

This tutorial is concerned with implementing a straightforward evolutionary algorithm for solving a simple continuous problem involving two decision variables. Note that the algorithmic scheme designed is very similar to the one introduced in Section 3 (population-based, generational method, uses two parents per offspring). Hence, some of the pieces of code will be the same. Thus, they will not be discussed for the sake of conciseness.

4.1. Problem definition

The problem tackled consists of only two decision variables whose feasible values are in $[0, 1]$ intervals for simplicity. This way, its so-called fitness landscape will be renderable using a 3D plot, providing thus a better insight into the problem and the search process imposed by the implemented optimizer. One can implement such an easy-to-comprehend simple benchmark by utilizing kernel-like functions, e.g., Gaussian-like ones. Precisely, this tutorial uses the kernels of two decision variables, x_1 and x_2 , in the following form:

$$k(x_1, x_2)^{\alpha, m, c_{x_1}, c_{x_2}} = \alpha e^{-(m^2((x_1 - c_{x_1})^2 + (x_2 - c_{x_2})^2))}, \quad (4)$$

where α can be considered an amplitude, m a distance-to-kernel multiplier, and c_{x_1} and c_{x_2} the center of a kernel.

Using kernels in a test function makes the overall fitness function tractable. Their graphical interpretation in the fitness landscape is that they constitute “hills,” and the goal will usually be to find the highest one (the maximum will often be close to the highest hill). This tutorial will use a fitness function composed of the following kernels:

$$\begin{aligned} \max f(x_1, x_2) = & k(x_1, x_2)^{2.5, 5.0, 0.7, 0.3} + \\ & k(x_1, x_2)^{1.0, 6.0, 0.2, 0.2} + k(x_1, x_2)^{1.5, 6.0, 0.3, 0.6} + \\ & k(x_1, x_2)^{1.2, 3.0, 0.7, 0.9} + k(x_1, x_2)^{1.7, 14.0, 0.35, 0.35} + \\ & k(x_1, x_2)^{1.4, 6.5, 0.6, 0.6} + k(x_1, x_2)^{2.0, 10.0, 0.2, 0.9}. \end{aligned}$$

The fitness landscape of this function is depicted in Figure 12, and the optimum is located near $[x_1 = 0.7, x_2 = 0.3]$ point (but not exactly in it).

4.2. Solution approach

The evolutionary method implemented to solve the problem introduced in Section 4.1 follows the same evolutionary scheme as the method developed in Section 3, i.e.:

- It uses a population-based scheme: a whole population of offspring solutions is created in one generation.
- It is assumed that two parents are selected per one offspring.
- The overall flow follows the pseudocode presented in Algorithm 1.
- The default fields for storing specimen-related data are used.
- A direct specimen representation is used (2-element double decision vector).

Therefore, the overall composition of the used phases and the design of the method’s bundle are very similar to the ones introduced in Section 3. Therefore, this document will not discuss these aspects in detail to avoid redundancy.

4.3. Designed algorithm

First, it is worth getting acquainted with the *Utils* class (*t1_t10.t2_continuous_problem.common* package), which provides practical static methods. For instance, Listing 45 brings methods related to calculating the objective function value (see the straightforward *Kernel* class in the same package).

Listing 45: Fitness-related static methods in the *Utils* class

```
/**
 * Creates the default problem instance.
 *
 * @return array of kernels
 */
public static Kernel[] getDefaultKernels()
{
    return new Kernel[]
    {
```


Figure 11: The final multi-plot window

Figure 12: The fitness landscape of the continuous problem

```

*/
public static double evaluatePoint(double
    x1, double x2, Kernel[] kernels)
{
    double sum = 0.0d;
    for (Kernel k : kernels) sum += k.
        evaluate(x1, x2);
    return sum;
}

```

Other auxiliary methods worth mentioning are the ones presented in Listing 46 (one of them is a runnable “main” method). They illustrate the problem’s fitness landscape using a 3D plot (they run the visualization window). The example outcomes of executing the main method are presented in Figure 13. This figure concerns three discretization levels: 50, 200, and 1000 (the number of equally spaced points used per X and Z axes). Note that the fitness landscape is illustrated using a regular scatter plot, but it would be more convenient to use a surface plot instead. However, it has not been implemented in JECDM yet (but is in plans for future updates).

```

10 new Kernel(2.5d, 5.0d, 0.7d, 0.3d),
11 new Kernel(1.0d, 6.0d, 0.2d, 0.2d),
12 new Kernel(1.5d, 6.0d, 0.3d, 0.6d),
13 new Kernel(1.2d, 3.0d, 0.7d, 0.9d),
14 new Kernel(1.7d, 14.0d, 0.35d, 0.35d),
15 new Kernel(1.4d, 6.5d, 0.6d, 0.6d),
16 new Kernel(2.0d, 10.0d, 0.2d, 0.9d),
17 };
18 }
19
20 /**
21  * Evaluates a point [x1, x2] given the
22  * kernel functions.
23  *
24  * @param x1 the first coordinate
25  * @param x2 the second coordinate
26  * @param kernels kernels used
27  * @return final evaluation (sum of kernel
28  * values)

```

Listing 46: Static methods in the Utils class related to displaying the fitness landscape

```

/**
 * Auxiliary method that generates an input
 * data for the visualization module (
 * double[][]) that illustrates
 * the fitness landscape of the tackled
 * problem. The data points are three-
 * element tuples, where the first (X)
 * and the third (Z) attribute are x1 and
 * x2 coordinates, while the second
 * attribute (Y) is the associated kernel-
 * based
 * evaluation.
 *
 * @param discdiscretization level (number
 * of divisions on x1 and x2 dimensions)
 * @param kernels kernels used
 * @return data to be visualized
 */

```


Figure 13: Fitness landscape visualized using Plot3D. Three different discretization levels were used: 50, 200, and 1000.

```

public static double[][]
    getFitnessLandscape(int disc, Kernel[]
        kernels)
{
    int div = disc - 1;
    int total = disc * disc;
    double[][] data = new double[total][3];
    int idx = 0;
    for (int i = 0; i < disc; i++)
    {
        for (int j = 0; j < disc; j++)
        {
            data[idx][0] = (double) i / div;
            data[idx][2] = (double) j / div;
            data[idx][1] = evaluatePoint(data[idx
                ][0], data[idx][2], kernels);
            idx++;
        }
    }
    return data;
}

/**
 * Runs the visualization of the fitness
 * landscape.
 *
 * @param args not used
 */
public static void main(String[] args)
{
    Kernel[] kernels = getDefaultKernels();
    double[][] data = getFitnessLandscape
        (1000, kernels);

    Plot3D plot3D =
        createDedicatedScatterPlot();
    Frame frame = new Frame(plot3D, 0.5f);

    RightClickPopupMenu menu = new
        RightClickPopupMenu();
    menu.addItem(new SaveAsImage());

```

```

plot3D.getController().
    addRightClickPopupMenu(menu);

AbstractScheme scheme = new WhiteScheme()
    ;
scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
    MARGIN_RIGHT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
    0.25f);
scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
    MARGIN_TOP_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
    0.0f);
scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
    MARGIN_BOTTOM_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER
    , 0.0f);
scheme._size.put(SizeFields.
    MARGIN_LEFT_RELATIVE_SIZE_MULTIPLIER,
    0.0f);

plot3D.updateScheme(scheme);

IDataSet ds = DataSet.getFor3D("Fitness
    landscape", data, new MarkerStyle(0.01
    f, Gradient.getViridisGradient(), 1,
    Marker.SPHERE_LOW_POLY_3D));
plot3D.getModel().setDataSet(ds, true);

frame.setVisible(true);
}

```

The following sections present the implementations of the *IConstruct*, *IReproduce*, and *IEvaluate* interfaces made for this tutorial. Note that the bundle class (see *ContEABundle* class) will not be discussed as it is a straightforward adaptation of its counterpart for solving the knapsack problem.

4.3.1. Constructor

Source: *t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t2_continuous_problem.common.ContConstructor*

Listing 47 brings the “*createInitialPopulation*” method implemented to solve the tackled 2-variable continuous problem. The

code is plain. It creates a specimen array of size “population-Size” and instantiates each specimen with a randomly generated two-element double vector (the drawn numbers are in the [0-1] bounds).

Listing 47: ContConstructor class (“createInitialPopulation” method)

```

/**
 * Creates initial population (array of
 * specimens) of size ‘‘population size’’.
 * The population consists of random
 * solutions to the 2-variable continuous
 * problem.
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @return specimen array
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 *         be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public ArrayList<Specimen>
    createInitialPopulation(EA ea) throws
    PhaseException
{
    int ps = ea.getPopulationSize(); //
    number of specimens = population size
    ArrayList<Specimen> specimens = new
    ArrayList<>(ps); // instantiate the
    array
    for (int i = 0; i < ps; i++) // iterate
    the required number of times
    {
        Specimen s = new Specimen(1); // 1
        criterion: value function
        Chromosome c = new Chromosome(new
        double []{ea.getRNG().nextDouble(),
        ea.getRNG().nextDouble()}); //
        random
        // x1 and x2 coordinates in [0, 1]
        bounds.
        s.setChromosome(c); // set specimen’s
        chromosome
        specimens.add(s); // store the specimen
    }
    return specimens;
}

```

4.3.2. Reproducer

Source: *t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t2_continuous_problem.common.ContReproducer*

This implementation follows the standard reproduction scheme in which two parents are crossed over to construct the offspring, followed by applying the mutation operator on this newly created solution. As for the crossover operator, a Simulated Binary Crossover [1] (SBX) is employed (see the *reproduction.operators.crossover* package). This implementation crosses over the elements of parents’ decision vectors (index-wise). The final offspring result is assumed to be closer to one

of the parents (selection follows the uniform distribution; an application of SBX creates two values, each closer to a different parent). A Polynomial Mutation [2] (PM) is used regarding the mutation operator.

Note that the initial release of JECMD also includes a hybrid SBX mixed with a single-point operator (see the *SBXwithSP* class). The random policy regarding which of the two produced values should be selected (implemented in *SBX*) may destroy some useful subsequences occurring in decision vectors during the evolution. A single-point crossover can assist the SBX in resolving this problem. Specifically, *SBXwithSP* first determines the “cutting point” (as the regular single-point operator does). Then, the SBX operator that forces the new values to be closer to the values of one of the parents if their indices are “on the left” to the cutting point is applied. The values of the other parent are the reference for these variables that are “on the right”.

Listing 48 presents the *ContReproducer* class that implements the *IReproduce* interface. It instantiates the SBX and PM operators in the constructor. Note that these operators can be parameterized in various ways, and it is left to the reader to get acquainted with the details. In short, the SBX will be applied with a probability of 1.0 and a distribution index of 10.0. Furthermore, the parameterization exhibits how to specify the feasible bounds for the decision variables and set a value-check procedure (intended to correct the infeasible values). When it comes to PM, it will be applied with a probability of 0.5 to each decision variable of the offspring, and the distribution index is also set to 10.0. The bounds and the value check/repair procedure are set in the same way as in SBX.

The main “*createOffspring*” method is a straightforward adaptation of the *KnapsackReproduces* class for dealing with continuous decision variables (operates on double vectors).

Listing 48: ContReproducer class

```

/**
 * The implementation of IReproduce
 * interface. It is assumed that the
 * constructed size equals ea.
 * getOffspringSize().
 * Further, the number of parents per
 * offspring is two, and the number of
 * parent objects stored in the specimen
 * container
 * equals the offspring size. The offspring
 * specimens are constructed by applying
 * an SBX operator to parents’
 * double decision vectors, followed by
 * applying a polynomial mutation (with
 * probability of 1 / the number of items)
 * .
 * Both operators used a distribution index
 * of 10.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class ContReproducer implements
    IReproduce
{
    /**

```

```

    * SBX operator mixed with single point
      crossover.
    */
15 private final SBX _SBX;

/**
    * Polynomial mutation operator
    */
20 private final PM _PM;

/**
    * Parameterized constructor.
    *
    * @param R random number generator;
    */
25 public ContReproducer(IRandom R)
{
    // instantiate the crossover and
      mutation operators

    // SBX operator is used (distribution
      index of 10)
    SBX.Params pSBX = new SBX.Params(R, 1.0
      d, 10.0d);

    // bounds for the double decision
      variables (if null, the default [0,
      1] bounds are used if the value
      check
    // object is used (see below).
    pSBX._doubleBounds = new Range[]{Range.
      getNormalRange(), Range.
      getNormalRange()};
    // Used to correct infeasible variable
      values. Incorrect values are wrapped
      around the boundaries.
    // Can be null -> not used.
    pSBX._valueCheck = new Wrap();

35 _SBX = new SBX(pSBX);

    PM.Params pM = new PM.Params(R, 1.0d /
      2.0d, 10.0d);
    pM._valueCheck = new Wrap();
    pM._doubleBounds = pSBX._doubleBounds;
    // share the objects
    _PM = new PM(pM);
}

/**
50 * Creates an array of offspring
      specimens (of size equal to ‘‘
      offspring size’’).
    *
    * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
    * @return offspring specimens
    */
@Override
55 public ArrayList<Specimen>
      createOffspring(EA ea)
{
    int os = ea.getOffspringSize(); // get

```

```

      the offspring size
    ArrayList<Specimen> offspring = new
      ArrayList<>(os);
    for (int i = 0; i < os; i++)
    {
        Parents parents = ea.
          getSpecimensContainer().getParents
            ().get(i);
        Specimen p1 = parents._parents.get(0)
          ;
        Specimen p2 = parents._parents.get(1)
          ;
        double[] bv1 = p1.
          getDoubleDecisionVector();
        double[] bv2 = p2.
          getDoubleDecisionVector();
        double[] ob = _SBX.crossover(bv1, bv2
          );
        _PM.mutate(ob);

        // create the specimen
        Chromosome chromosome = new
          Chromosome(ob);
        Specimen specimen = new Specimen(2);
        specimen.setChromosome(chromosome);
        offspring.add(specimen);
    }
    return offspring;
}
}

```

4.3.3. Evaluator

Source: *t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.t2_continuous_problem.common.ContEvaluator*

The implementation of the evaluator class is self-explanatory (see the *ContEvaluator* class). The main “*evaluateSpecimens*” method is presented in Listing 49. It iterates over all input specimens and calculates their fitness, which is calculated using the kernels (provided via the constructor). The first two double values in the double decision vectors are derived and passed to the “*Utils.evaluatePoint*” method for this purpose. The final score is stored as the specimen’s performance and auxiliary value.

Listing 49: ContEvaluator class (“*evaluateSpecimens*” method)

```

/**
    * Evaluates specimens.
    *
    * @param specimens array of specimens to
      be evaluated
    * @throws PhaseException the exception can
      be thrown and propagated higher
    */
@Override
5 public void evaluateSpecimens(ArrayList<
      Specimen> specimens) throws
      PhaseException
{
    for (Specimen s : specimens)

```

```

{
    double [] x = s.getDoubleDecisionVector
        ();
    double fitness = Utils.evaluatePoint(x
        [0], x[1], _kernels);
    s.setEvaluations(new double []{fitness})
        ;
    s.setAuxScore(fitness);
}
}

```

flags: “*_addGeneration*” and “*_generationWhenConstructed*”. The “*_addGeneration*” flag, if set to true, will force adding a fourth element to constructed vectors: the current generation number (*ea.getCurrentGeneration()*), which may be helpful when coloring specimens based on the generation. The “*_generationWhenConstructed*” sets the interpretation of the “*generation*”. By default, the generation (if used) is derived from the current timestamp. Note that, however, each specimen stores information when it has been constructed (in which generation; such a number should be smaller (or equal) than the current generation)). Such data is stored in the specimen’s ID object and will be used if the “*_generationWhenConstructed*” flag is set to true (*s.getID()._generation*).

The expected final render produced by this tutorial’s source code is illustrated in Figure 15. The final population is marked using black dots (spheres), and it is evident that it has reached the global maximum.

4.4. Example experiments

This section shows how to use the designed evolutionary algorithm for solving the 2-variable continuous problem in practice. However, since the codes are very similar to those concerned in Section 3.4, this section will not elaborate on them to avoid repetitions.

4.4.1. Creating and running the algorithm

Source package:
t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.
t2_continuous_problem.t1

This section shows how to create and run the evolutionary method. The code is a straightforward adaptation of the one introduced in Listing 42. The final expected outcome that should be printed in the console is presented in Figure 14 (only initial generations and a few of the best specimens are reported).

4.4.2. Reporting the performance using a scatter plot (the last generation)

Source package:
t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.
t2_continuous_problem.t2

The following tutorial exhibits how to illustrate the final population on the fitness landscape rendered using a 3D plot. The overall procedure is straightforward. A suitably parameterized *DataUpdater* has to be constructed, and it should include two data sources: a fixed data set that represents the fitness landscape and a data set associated with the final population. When it comes to the first, the input data points that can be derived via the “*Utils.getFitnessLandscape*” method are in the following form: $[x_1, fitness, x_2]$. Therefore, a dedicated implementation of *IDataSource* that would transform the population members into compatible vectors is required. Example one is brought as *ContEASource* class, and its code is presented in Listing 50.

The “*createData*” method of the *ContEASource* class transforms specimens’ data into vectors that take the following form: [*specimen’s first decision variable value, specimen’s first performance value, specimen’s second decision variable value*], and aggregates them into a matrix (to be returned). Hence, such formulated data is compatible with *Plot3D* (and, thus, can be illustrated on a 3D plot with a fitness landscape). The class accepts two additional parameterization

Listing 50: ContEASource class

```

/**
 * Dedicated data source. Creates data
 * point in the following form: [specimen
 * first decision variable (x-coordinate);
 * specimen performance value; specimen
 * second decision variable (y-coordinate)
 * ].
 *
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class ContEASource extends
    AbstractEASource implements IDataSource
{
    /**
     * If true, the generation number will be
     * added as the fourth attribute.
     */
    private final boolean _addGeneration;

    /**
     * If true (and the ‘add generation’
     * flag is true), the specimen
     * individual timestamp will be used
     * instead of
     * the current timestamp’s generation
     * number.
     */
    private final boolean
        _generationWhenConstructed;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param eareference to the associated
     * EA
     * @param addGeneration if true, the
     * generation number will be added as
     * the fourth attribute
     * @param generationWhenConstructed if
     * true (and the ‘add generation’ flag
     * is true), the specimen individual

```

```

Initialization (generation = 0):
Specimen = 0 0 0 99: [value = 2.5256044725767524; aux = 2.5256044725767524] 0,6916 0,3402
Specimen = 0 0 0 86: [value = 2.494657336789598; aux = 2.494657336789598] 0,6628 0,3161
Specimen = 0 0 0 71: [value = 2.2157701658098587; aux = 2.2157701658098587] 0,6788 0,4071
Specimen = 0 0 0 83: [value = 2.122819579423893; aux = 2.122819579423893] 0,6111 0,6211
Specimen = 0 0 0 37: [value = 2.0612459965897543; aux = 2.0612459965897543] 0,6348 0,5417
Generation = 1:
Specimen = 0 1 0 0: [value = 2.5256044725767524; aux = 2.5256044725767524] 0,6916 0,3402
Specimen = 0 1 0 1: [value = 2.494657336789598; aux = 2.494657336789598] 0,6628 0,3161
Specimen = 0 1 0 2: [value = 2.2157701658098587; aux = 2.2157701658098587] 0,6788 0,4071
Specimen = 0 1 0 3: [value = 2.122819579423893; aux = 2.122819579423893] 0,6111 0,6211
Specimen = 0 1 0 4: [value = 2.0612459965897543; aux = 2.0612459965897543] 0,6348 0,5417
Generation = 2:
Specimen = 0 1 0 0: [value = 2.5256044725767524; aux = 2.5256044725767524] 0,6916 0,3402
Specimen = 0 1 0 1: [value = 2.494657336789598; aux = 2.494657336789598] 0,6628 0,3161
Specimen = 0 2 0 73: [value = 2.323812153699703; aux = 2.323812153699703] 0,7628 0,3069
Specimen = 0 2 0 75: [value = 2.2735443429121074; aux = 2.2735443429121074] 0,7285 0,3816
Specimen = 0 1 0 2: [value = 2.2157701658098587; aux = 2.2157701658098587] 0,6788 0,4071
Generation = 3:
Specimen = 0 3 0 46: [value = 2.5313436029763627; aux = 2.5313436029763627] 0,6937 0,3385
Specimen = 0 3 0 43: [value = 2.5303722757224962; aux = 2.5303722757224962] 0,6898 0,3380
Specimen = 0 1 0 0: [value = 2.5256044725767524; aux = 2.5256044725767524] 0,6916 0,3402
Specimen = 0 1 0 1: [value = 2.494657336789598; aux = 2.494657336789598] 0,6628 0,3161
Specimen = 0 3 0 6: [value = 2.370232043663361; aux = 2.370232043663361] 0,7400 0,3519
Generation = 4:

```

Figure 14: Expected console output

<pre> timestamp will be used instead of the current timestamp's generation number. */ public ContEASource(EA ea, boolean addGeneration, boolean generationWhenConstructed) { super(ea, new PopulationGetter()); _addGeneration = addGeneration; _generationWhenConstructed = generationWhenConstructed; } /** * Creates data point in the following * form: [specimen first decision * variable (x-coordinate); specimen * performance value; * specimen second decision variable (y- * coordinate)]. * </pre>	<pre> * @return new data */ @Override public double [][] createData() { ArrayList<Specimen> specimens = getDefaultSpecimens(); double [][] data; if (_addGeneration) data = new double[specimens.size()][4]; else data = new double[specimens.size()][3]; Specimen s; for (int i = 0; i < specimens.size(); i ++) { s = specimens.get(i); data[i][0] = s. getDoubleDecisionVector()[0]; data[i][1] = s.getEvaluations()[0]; data[i][2] = s. </pre>
--	--

Figure 15: The final scatter plot (solutions from the last generation are illustrated)

```

55     getDoubleDecisionVector() [1];
    if (_addGeneration)
    {
        if (_generationWhenConstructed)
            data[i][3] = s.getID().
                _generation; // generation when
                constructed
        else data[i][3] = _ea.
            getCurrentGeneration(); //
            current timestamp's generation
            no.
    }
60 }
    return data;
}

```

4.4.3. Reporting the performance using a scatter plot (all generations)

Source package:
t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.
t2_continuous_problem.t3

This tutorial adapts the previous one to illustrate all populations generated throughout the evolution, each rendered using a different gradient color based on the generation number. The expected final renders are illustrated in Figure 16 and 17. The former illustrates the data set for which the generation number was retrieved from the current timestamp. As for the latter, the generation was obtained from the specimen ID (represents when the specimen was constructed). Consequently, the first shows when the population was in subsequent generations as a whole entity, while the latter exhibits when the population members were constructed.

Figure 16: The final scatter plot (all populations are illustrated, generation numbers are taken from the current timestamp)

4.4.4. Reporting the performance using a multi-plot visualization window

Source package:
t1_t10.t2_evolutionary_computation_module.
t2_continuous_problem.t4

This final tutorial shows how to construct a two-plot visualization window. One plot is a 3D plot illustrating the fitness landscape and constructed populations throughout generations, while the other is a convergence plot revealing how the over-

all population fitness changed during the optimization process. The expected final render is depicted in Figure 18.

References

- [1] Deb, K., Agrawal, R.B., 1994. Simulated Binary Crossover for Continuous Search Space. Technical Report IITK/ME/SMD-94027. Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, India.
- [2] Deb, K., Mayank, G., 1996. A Combined Genetic Adaptive Search GeneAS for Engineering Design. Computer Science and Informatics 26, 30-45.

Figure 17: The final scatter plot (all populations are illustrated, generation numbers are taken from specimens' creation times)

- [3] Deb, K., Pratap, A., Agarwal, S., Meyarivan, T., 2000. A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 6, 182–197. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/4235.996017>.
- [4] Deb, K., Thiele, L., Laumanns, M., Zitzler, E., 2005. *Scalable Test Problems for Evolutionary Multiobjective Optimization*. Springer London, London. pp. 105–145. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/1-84628-137-7_6.
- [5] Huband, S., Hingston, P., Barone, L., While, L., 2006. A review of multiobjective test problems and a scalable test problem toolkit. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 10, 477–506. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2005.861417>.
- [6] Zhang, Q., Li, H., 2007. MOEA/D: A multiobjective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 11, 712–731. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2007.892759>.

Figure 18: The final multi-plot window